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Structural and evolutionary insights into the isoprene monooxygenases

Journal:	<i>FEMS Microbiology Ecology</i>
Manuscript ID	FEMSEC-25-10-0260.R3
Manuscript Type:	Research article
Date Submitted by the Author:	19-Jan-2026
Complete List of Authors:	Larke-Mejia, Nasmille; University of Copenhagen, Terrestrial Ecology Larke-Mejía, Nasmille; University of Copenhagen, Department of Biology de Oliveira Martins, Leonardo; University of Liverpool, Dept Electrical Engineering and Electronics Murrell, Colin; University of East Anglia, Science
Keywords:	isoprene monooxygenase, IsoA, soluble di-iron monooxygenase, methane monooxygenase, protein sequence evolution, structural modelling

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1 **Structural and evolutionary insights into the isoprene monooxygenases**

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4 3 Larke-Mejía, N.L.^{a, b*}, de Oliveira Martins, L.^c and Murrell, J.C.^b

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6
7 5 ^aCenter for Volatile Interactions (VOLT), Department of Biology, University of Copenhagen,
8
9 6 Universitetsparken 15, Copenhagen Ø, 2100, Denmark.

10
11 7 ^bSchool of Environmental Sciences, University of East Anglia, Norwich, NR4 7TJ, UK.

12
13 8 ^cSignal Processing Group, Dept Electrical Engineering and Electronics, University of Liverpool, L69
14 9 7ZF, Liverpool, UK.

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For Peer Review

41
42 25 ***Corresponding author:**

43 26 Nasmille L. Larke-Mejía

44
45 27 Email: nala@bio.ku.dk

46
47 28 Center for Volatile Interactions (VOLT), Department of Biology, University of Copenhagen,
48
49 29 Universitetsparken 15, Copenhagen Ø, 2100, Denmark

50 30 VOLT mobile number: +45 23 84 00 79

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Abstract

Isoprene, a highly reactive biogenic volatile organic compound (VOC) emitted by terrestrial vegetation, influences atmospheric chemistry but its microbial degradation remains poorly understood. Aerobic degradation begins with isoprene monooxygenase (IsoMO), a multicomponent di-iron monooxygenase encoded by the *isoABCDEF* cluster, with *isoGHIJ* supporting downstream steps. We analysed *iso* gene clusters from eleven confirmed isoprene degraders, reconstructed amino acid sequence phylogenies and generated structural models of IsoMO components using mainly AlphaFold2. IsoA, IsoE, and IsoB formed a highly conserved $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$ monooxygenase core (IsoMO core) whose predicted architecture and closely resembled the soluble methane monooxygenase (sMMO) hydroxylase, revealing a shared di-iron catalytic framework adapted to distinct hydrocarbon substrates. IsoA was the most conserved subunit and remains a reliable molecular marker for isoprene degradation. This work presents the first detailed structural model of an IsoMO core and reveals its deep relationship to other soluble di-iron monooxygenases. Together these results provide a molecular foundation for future mechanistic, ecological and inhibitor-based studies linking enzyme-level specificity to microbial control of isoprene turnover under changing climate conditions.

Keywords: isoprene degradation, isoprene monooxygenase, IsoA, soluble di-iron monooxygenase, methane monooxygenase, protein sequence evolution, structural modelling, functional marker genes

50 Introduction

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52
53 Isoprene (2-methyl-1,3-butadiene) is a highly reactive C₅ hydrocarbon and the most abundantly
54 emitted non-methane biogenic volatile organic compound (BVOC), released primarily by terrestrial
55 plants, with global emissions comparable to methane at rates exceeding ~ 500 Tg per year (Guenther et
56 al., 2012; reviewed in Carrión et al., 2020). In the atmosphere, isoprene plays a major role in the
57 formation of tropospheric ozone and secondary organic aerosols (SOAs), which impact air quality,
58 cloud properties, and radiative forcing (Claeys et al., 2004; Wennberg et al., 2018; Shen et al., 2024).
59 While its atmospheric chemistry is well characterized, microbial degradation of isoprene is a new
60 research area (reviewed in Dawson et al., 2023).

61
62 Recent evidence has shown that bacteria from diverse environments (soil, aquatic and leaf surfaces)
63 can degrade isoprene, making microbial degradation the only known biological sink of atmospheric
64 isoprene (McGenity et al., 2018; Carrión et al., 2020). In some ecosystems, such as *Sphagnum*-
65 dominated peatlands, microbial uptake of isoprene may even counterbalance net emissions from the
66 moss (Crombie et al., 2025).

67
68 Aerobic isoprene degradation (*iso*-type, Figure S1) is initiated by isoprene monooxygenase (IsoMO)
69 encoded by the *isoABCDEF* genes. IsoMO is a multicomponent di-iron monooxygenase enzyme from
70 Group 1 of the soluble di-iron centre monooxygenase family (SDIMO) essential for the first step of
71 isoprene degradation (Crombie et al., 2015; Dawson et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2025). This
72 monooxygenation step yields (R)-epoxyisoprene (van Hylckama Vlieg et al., 2000), a toxic
73 intermediate which is further processed and detoxified via a glutathione-dependent pathway encoded
74 by *isoGHIJ* (Rix et al., 2023). The core *iso* gene cluster (*iso* cluster) typically comprises 11 genes
75 (*isoA-isoJ*, *aldH*) (Dawson et al., 2023). Within IsoMO monooxygenase core (IsoMO core: $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$;
76 Zhou et al. 1998; Leahy et al. 2003), IsoA encodes the central catalytic α -subunit component, which
77 contains a di-iron active site (van Hylckama Vlieg et al., 1998) and IsoE and IsoB encode the
78 associated β -subunit and γ -subunits, respectively (van Hylckama Vlieg et al., 2000). The IsoMO also
79 contains IsoC (a Rieske-type ferredoxin), IsoD (a coupling protein), and IsoF (an FMN-containing
80 reductase component) that extract electrons from NADH and transfers them to the di-iron center in the
81 monooxygenase α -subunit (Zhou et al., 1998; van Hylckama Vlieg et al., 2000), as seen with other

82 SDIMO such as methane and toluene monooxygenases (Rosenzweig et al., 1997; Notomista et al.,
83 2003; Wang et al., 2014).

84

85 The detoxification module pathway includes first IsoI, an isoprene pathway-specific glutathione S-
86 transferase (GST) (van Hylckama Vlieg et al., 1998; Van Hylckama Vlieg et al., 1999), which
87 conjugates epoxyisoprene with glutathione (GSH) to produce HGMB (1-hydroxy-2-glutathionyl-2-
88 methyl-3-butene) (Rix et al., 2023). IsoH (an NAD⁺-dependent dehydrogenase) which sequentially
89 oxidizes HGMB in two NAD⁺-dependent steps to form GMBA (2-glutathionyl-2-methyl-3-butanoic
90 acid) (Rix et al., 2023). IsoG (a putative CoA-transferase) then converts GMBA into GMBA-CoA by
91 attaching coenzyme A (from an unknown source). In the same step IsoJ, encodes for the second
92 isoprene pathway-specific GST assigned to the Actino-like class of GST (Haarmann et al., 2025), that
93 removes oxidized glutathione (GSSG) from GMBA-CoA, producing MBE-CoA (2-methyl-3-hydroxy-
94 butenyl-CoA, Dawson et al., 2022; Rix et al., 2023). The final gene in the cluster is *aldH* which
95 encodes a putative aldehyde dehydrogenase thought to oxidize intermediates of HGMB to GMBA
96 (Dawson et al., 2022) and likely catalyzes a second NAD⁺-dependent oxidation step as in the
97 StyH/AldH1 system of styrene metabolism (Dawson et al., 2023; Rix et al., 2023).

98

99 Within the *iso* cluster, *isoA* is the most conserved gene and has been widely used as a molecular
100 marker for detecting and anchoring *iso* cluster genes from isoprene degraders detected in
101 environmental DNA using PCR and qPCR assays and metagenomics (El Khawand et al., 2016; Larke-
102 Mejía et al., 2019; Carrión et al., 2020). IsoA shares ancestry with MmoX (Group 3 SDIMO, Yang et
103 al., 2025), the catalytic α -subunit of soluble methane monooxygenase (sMMO), and with the toluene
104 and alkene monooxygenases (Leahy et al., 2003; Coleman et al., 2006; McGenity et al., 2018).
105 Although sMMO has been thoroughly characterized (Rosenzweig et al., 1993; Hakemian and
106 Rosenzweig, 2007), detailed structural insights into IsoA are lacking.

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108 *Iso*-type degraders have been isolated from a wide range of environments yet the evolutionary history,
109 modular organization, and structure-to-function relationships of the *iso* cluster are poorly understood
110 and no systematic phylogenetic or structural comparison of the proteins encoded in the full *isoA-J*,
111 *aldH* cluster has been performed. Also, the evolutionary congruence of individual proteins, patterns of
112 duplication within the gene cluster, and the structural similarity of IsoA to other SDIMO α -subunits
113 remain unexplored. To address this, we conducted a comparative genomic and structural analysis of
114 the *iso* cluster in confirmed *iso*-type isoprene-degrading bacteria. Our aims were to: (i) visualise the

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1 115 gene order and modular structure of the core *iso* cluster; (ii) construct nucleotide and protein
2 116 phylogenies to evaluate evolutionary congruence across the cluster; (iii) compare IsoA to
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4 117 representative SDIMO α -subunits to identify conserved functional motifs; and (iv) use AlphaFold2
5 118 monomer and multimer modelling and structural alignment to explore IsoA structure and active site
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7 119 architecture.
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11 121 Anchored by the well-characterized sMMO framework, this study places IsoMO within the broader
12 122 evolutionary landscape of microbial one-carbon (C₁) and hydrocarbon monooxygenases. Our
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14 123 integrated approach provides the first detailed structural and phylogenetic comparison of IsoA with
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16 124 MmoX and lays the groundwork for future biochemical and ecological studies of isoprene metabolism.
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18 125 We hypothesized that: (i) phylogenetic signals within the *iso* cluster reflect vertical inheritance with
19 126 taxon-specific modularity; (ii) IsoA is the most conserved and functionally constrained gene within the
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21 127 cluster, with structural features similar to MmoX; and (iii) IsoA and MmoX share conserved catalytic
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23 128 residues, reflecting mechanistic parallels in hydrocarbon oxidation.
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129 **Methods**

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132 *Genome selection and dataset compilation*

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134 18 bacterial genomes representing extant *iso*-type isoprene-degrading strains were identified, 15 Gram-
135 positive strains, primarily from the genus *Rhodococcus* (e.g., *Rh.* AD45, *Rh. opacus* PD630, *Rh.* LB1,
136 *Rh.* WS7), two *Gordonia* (*Gordonia* sp. i37 and *Gordonia* sp. OPL2), *Mycobacterium* sp. AT1, and
137 *Nocardioides* sp. WS12 plus three Gram-negative representatives of the Comamonadaceae family
138 (*Ramlibacter* sp. WS9, *Variovorax* sp. WS11, and *Sphingopyxis* sp. OPL5). From this dataset, 11
139 genomes were selected for downstream analyses based on published reports of isoprene catabolism,
140 active enrichment in DNA-SIP experiments, and the presence of key catabolic genes, such as *isoA*.
141 Assembly statistics (e.g., N50, L50, genome size, GC content, and supporting references) are provided
142 in Table S1. These 11 isolates also represent phylogenetic breadth, ecological diversity (soil,
143 freshwater, and phyllosphere origins), and known variation in *iso* cluster structure (Table 1).

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146 *Identification and extraction of isoprene metabolic gene clusters*

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148 Gene clusters were identified in the genomes of 11 isoprene-degrading bacterial isolates. Genomic
149 assemblies were obtained in FASTA format (.fna) from NCBI or locally-generated assemblies. Initial
150 cluster coordinates were based on the NCBI GenBank public annotation and homology to known *isoA*-
151 containing regions. Where required, complete contigs were searched using BLAST to identify the
152 location of *isoA* homologues. To validate and refine cluster extraction, an IsoA protein sequence
153 database was used as a query in a tblastn search against all genome contigs. Each genome was split
154 into individual contig files using Biopython (Cock et al., 2009) and combined into a single nucleotide
155 BLAST database using makeblastdb (NCBI BLAST+ suite v 2.12.0+, (Camacho et al., 2009)).
156 Matching contigs were filtered to retain the top-scoring *isoA*-containing regions, and from these
157 contigs the whole identifiable *iso* operon was extracted with an additional ± 2 kb of flanking sequence
158 at each side of the operon (total region varied from 13kb to 29kb between isolates) and stored in a
159 curated directory. Where needed, specific contigs from GenBank (e.g., NZ_RKME01000032.1 for
160 *Gordonia* sp. OPL2) were targeted to extract the correct cluster. During trimming, GenBank records

1 161 were validated to retain the molecule_type annotation and any features located entirely within the
2 162 extracted region were retained and coordinate-shifted accordingly.

7 165 *Functional annotation, visualization and comparative analysis*

9 166
10 167 All curated *isoA* cluster regions were re-annotated using Bakta (v1.11.4, (Schwengers et al. 2021)
12 168 against the full Bakta reference database (Zenodo, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7997310). Annotated .gbk
14 169 files for each *iso* cluster were then visualized in Figure 1 and compared across the 11 isoprene-
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16 170 degrading isolates using Clinker (v0.0.31; Gilchrist and Chooi, 2021). Where necessary, whole cluster
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18 171 orientation and gene labels were manually curated to improve interpretability.

23 174 *iso cluster identification and comparative genomics*

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26 176 The 11 *iso* genes (*isoA-J*, *aldH*, referred to here collectively as the 11 *iso* genes) were identified in the
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28 177 selected genomes and cluster boundaries were defined by syntenic neighborhood, proximity, and
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30 178 functional annotations. Protein and nucleotide sequences were extracted for each gene and compiled
31 179 into FASTA files for further analysis (Table S2).

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35 181 Pairwise sequence similarity was assessed using BLASTn (nucleotide) and BLASTp (protein) with
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37 182 default parameters. Percent identity matrices were generated for each gene (protein: Table S3) and
38 183 mean pairwise identity values were computed and grouped by Gram type (Gram+:Gram+, Gram-
39 :Gram-, Gram+:Gram-), to quantify taxonomic divergence (Table S4).

45 187 *Phylogenetic and sequence alignment analyses*

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47 188
48 189 DNA and predicted amino acid sequences for the 11 *iso* cluster genes from each of the 11 genomes
50 190 (Table 1) were used to infer gene-by-gene phylogenies. Multiple sequence protein alignment was
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52 191 generated using MAFFT v7.505 (Kato and Standley, 2013) with the L-INS-i strategy and trimmed
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54 192 with trimAl v1.4 (Capella-Gutiérrez et al., 2009) using the auto mode. For each full protein alignment,
55 193 maximum likelihood phylogenetic trees (Figures S2A–S12A) were constructed with IQTREE2 v2.4.0

1 194 (Minh et al., 2020) under an LG evolutionary model (Le and Gascuel, 2008) with gamma
2 195 heterogeneity (Yang, 1994). Branching support was assessed with 10,000 ultrafast bootstrap replicates
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4 196 as implemented in IQTREE2 (Hoang et al., 2018), where the best tree as well as each bootstrap
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6 197 replicate were further optimised using a nearest neighbor interchange search. The same procedure was
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8 198 used for the DNA alignment, under an HKY model (Hasegawa et al., 1985) with gamma heterogeneity
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10 199 (Yang, 1994).

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12 201 For visualisation and protein structure prediction purposes, the alignment was visualised with ESPript
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14 202 3.0 (Robert and Gouet, 2014) (Figures S2B–S12B) with secondary structure elements annotated using
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16 203 *Rh* sp. AD45 as a reference for numbering. Conserved sequence motifs characteristic of di-iron
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18 204 monooxygenases motifs were identified manually and verified using UniProt (UniProt Consortium,
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20 205 2025) and PDB annotations (Zardecki et al., 2022).

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23 207 To assess phylogenetic congruence among genes and input data source, normalised tree distances
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25 208 between all maximum likelihood tree pairs were calculated, including comparisons between amino
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27 209 acid-derived and nucleotide-derived trees. For these calculations, the phangorn library for R was used
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29 210 (Schliep, 2011). Specifically, we calculated four distances between all tree pairs: the Robinson Foulds
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31 211 (RF) (Robinson and Foulds, 1981) and the subtree prune and regraft (SPR) (de Oliveira Martins et al.,
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33 212 2008) normalised by their maximum values. These distances only take the topologies into account, and
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35 213 therefore to account also for branch lengths, we employed the weighted RF (Robinson and Foulds,
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37 214 1979) and the branch score distances (Kuhner and Felsenstein, 1984) on rescaled branch lengths, so
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39 215 that trees had comparable phylogenetic diversity. All distances were visualised as a heatmap to
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41 216 highlight clusters of phylogenetically similar histories and congruent genes, and their distribution was
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43 217 summarised in a histogram to assess the degree of overall topological similarity. Multidimensional
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45 218 scaling (MDS) was applied to the distance matrices using the cmdscale function in R v4.3.1 to project
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47 219 relationships among gene trees into two-dimensions, enabling visual detection of phylogenetically
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49 220 coherent gene modules. Figures were generated using ggplot2 v3.4.2 and ggtree (Yu et al., 2017) in R,
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51 221 and for visualisation purposes the trees were re-rooted by midpoint rooting using the phangorn library
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53 222 (Schliep, 2011).

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56 225 *Structural modelling of IsoMO subunits and complexes*
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227 Protein structure predictions were performed using AlphaFold2 implemented in ColabFold v1.5.2
228 (Mirdita et al., 2022), which integrates MMseqs2-based multiple sequence alignment (Steinegger and
229 Söding, 2017) and the AlphaFold2 inference pipeline (Jumper et al. 2021), using default parameters.
230 For each of the 11 genes, monomeric models were generated for both Gram-positive (*Rh.* AD45) and
231 Gram-negative *Variovorax* sp. WS11 (*V.* WS11) representatives (*Rh. opacus* PD630 was used in place
232 of *Rh.* AD45 for AldH1). For IsoA, additional dimeric models were generated using the AlphaFold2
233 “auto” model_type pipeline to evaluate conserved α_2 arrangements. A larger $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$ assembly was
234 subsequently modelled using AlphaFold2-Multimer v3 model_type, by combining multimer
235 predictions for IsoA + IsoB + 2×IsoE and 2×IsoA + 2×IsoB within PyMOL using the super alignment
236 command. This approach captured the canonical IsoMO core architecture (num_recycles = 1). The
237 final IsoMO core structure was reconstructed and verified with AlphaFold3 (Abramson et al., 2024).
238 Confidence scores (pLDDT, pTM, ipTM) for the modelled monomers/dimers and multimers were
239 generated using AlphaFold2 or AlphaFold3, respectively.

241 Structural visualisation, chain splitting, superposition, and residue highlighting were performed using
242 PyMOL v2.5 (Schrödinger and DeLano, 2020). IsoA models were additionally aligned to the
243 crystallographic structure of the soluble methane monooxygenase α -subunit MmoX (PDB ID: 1MTY;
244 Rosenzweig et al., 1993) after removal of non- α subunits. Iron-coordinating residues, conserved
245 motifs, and clade-specific loops were highlighted and labelled manually for clarity.

248 *Comparison of alpha-subunit sequences of different SDIMOs*

250 Protein sequences for the α -subunits of selected SDIMOs were compiled. IsoA sequences from the 11
251 isoprene degraders were included. A list of strains and accession numbers is provided in Table S5. The
252 dataset included six soluble methane monooxygenase (sMMO; MmoX) sequences from *Methylosinus*
253 *trichosporium* Ob3b, *Methylococcus capsulatus* (Bath), *Methylomonas methanica* MC09 (Boden et al.
254 2011; Zill et al. 2022), *Methylocella silvestris* BL2, *Methylocella tundrae* T4, and *Methylocella*
255 *palustris* BL2; butane monooxygenase (BmoX) from *Pseudomonas butanovora*; tetrahydrofuran
256 monooxygenase (ThmA) from *Pseudonocardia tetrahydrofuranoxydans*; propane monooxygenase
257 (PrmA) from *Gordonia* sp. TY5 and *Rh.* sp. RR1; propane monooxygenase (PmoC) from
258 *Mycobacterium* sp. M156; alkene monooxygenase (EtnC) from *Mycolicibacterium rhodesiae* JS60,
259 *Mycolicibacterium chubuense* NBB4, and *Nocardioides* sp. JS614; toluene ortho-monooxygenase

1 260 (TmoA3) from *Burkholderia cepacia* G4; toluene-4-monooxygenase (TmoA) from *Pseudomonas*
2 261 *mendocina* KR1; toluene-3-monooxygenase (TbuA) from *Ralstonia pickettii* PKO; and alkene
3
4 262 monooxygenase (XamoA) from *Xanthobacter autotrophicus* Py2.

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7 264 Multiple sequence alignment and maximum-likelihood trees were performed as described previously.

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9 265 The alignment (Figure S16) has *Rh. AD45 IsoA* as the structural reference for secondary structure
10
11 266 annotation and motif mapping. For the main SDIMO context tree (Figure 2), all IsoA sequences were
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13 267 retained along with one to two representative sequences per major SDIMO α -subunit clade (MmoX,
14 268 BmoX, PrmA, ThmA, TmoA) to highlight relationships without overloading the topology.

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19 271 *Residue-Level Comparison Between IsoA and MmoX*

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23 273 A focused alignment was constructed between the IsoA and MmoX sequences using MAFFT v7.505
24 274 (without trimming). Structural superpositions of IsoA monomers and dimers with MmoX (PDB:
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26 275 1MTY) were performed with PyMOL. Conserved secondary structural elements were inferred by
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28 276 aligning six representative MmoX sequences and visualized via ESPript, enabling cross-reference of α -
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30 277 helices, β -strands, and di-iron motifs between MmoX and IsoA (Figure 3; Figures S17 and S18).

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278 Results

280 Overview of *iso*-genes and genomic datasets

282 To investigate the diversity, conservation, and genomic context of the IsoMO and its associated
283 catabolic genes, we constructed a dataset of *iso* clusters from 11 confirmed bacterial genomes of *iso*-
284 type isoprene degraders from multiple taxonomic groups originating from diverse environments. These
285 included 8 Gram-positive strains, primarily from the genus *Rhodococcus*, along with representative
286 *Gordonia*, *Mycobacterium*, and *Nocardioides*, and the three Gram-negative isoprene degraders from
287 the family Comamonadaceae: *Ramlibacter* WS9, *Variovorax* WS11, and *Sphingopyxis* OPL5.

289 Although relatively few genomes are available, the dataset reflects broad taxonomic and ecological
290 diversity, with isolates recovered from estuarine, freshwater, soil and phyllosphere environments. Most
291 strains were obtained from enrichment experiments, using isoprene as the only source of carbon and
292 energy, often from leaves or soils associated with isoprene-emitting trees such as *Elaeis guineensis*,
293 *Populus alba*, and *Salix alba*. Following enrichment, bacteria isolates were purified and confirmed to
294 degrade isoprene through growth assays, along with detection of key *iso* genes (initially *isoA*). The
295 taxonomic affiliation, source of isolation, and relevant references for each strain are summarized in
296 Table 1, with detailed genome statistics provided in Table S1. Genome sizes ranged from 4.68 Mb to
297 12.7 Mb, and protein-coding genes varied from 4,400 to 10,800 per genome.

300 Organization and conservation of the *iso* gene cluster

302 Syntenic neighbourhood comparisons separate Gram-positive and Gram-negative taxa (Figure 1).
303 Homologous genes were identified by amino acid identity ($\geq 20\%$) and gene orientation was maintained
304 in the figure to reflect the native genomic organization and orientation of each gene. As expected, all
305 strains contained a conserved modular cluster of six genes encoding the IsoMO subunits (*isoA-F*),
306 typically followed by four glutathione-dependent genes (*isoG-J*). The aldehyde dehydrogenase gene
307 (*aldHI*), was located immediately downstream of *isoF* in most genomes, except for *Rh. AD45* in
308 which *aldHI* was absent from this locus (Dawson et al. 2020).

1 310 Two major patterns were apparent from the *iso* cluster visualization. Firstly, most *Rhodococcus*
2 311 genomes (except WS1, isolated at lower isoprene enrichment concentrations) showed a distinctive
3 312 modular organization characterized by duplications and rearrangements of the *isoGHIJ* module. This
4 313 suggests possible species-specific adaptation to environmental conditions or isoprene flux. Second,
5 314 Gram-positive and Gram-negative strains may be further distinguished by adjacent accessory genes. In
6 315 Gram-positives (*Rhodococcus*, *Nocardioides*, *Gordonia*, *Mycobacterium*), *gshA* was consistently
7 316 positioned upstream of *isoG*, *gshB* downstream of *isoF* also observed by Haarmann et al., 2025, and
8 317 *marR*-like regulator was usually present (absent only in *Mycobacterium*, which instead encoded MCE
9 318 family proteins and LysR-type regulator). In Gram-negatives (*Sphingopyxis*, *Ramlibacter*,
10 319 *Variovorax*), *gorA* (in charge of catalyzing glutathione disulfide to reduced glutathione; UniprotKB
11 320 P06715) was present upstream of *isoF*, and two of the genomes also carried a *lysR*-type regulator gene.
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23 323 **Pairwise amino acid sequence conservation of IsoMO and detoxification proteins**

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25 325 To further characterize the proteins encoded by the *iso* cluster, we calculated average amino acid
26 326 sequence lengths across the 11 selected genomes (Table S2). The IsoMO proteins were highly
27 327 consistent in length, with IsoA averaging 425 amino acids (± 1), IsoB 334 (± 2), IsoC 184 (± 1), IsoD
28 328 194 (± 3), IsoE 381 (± 2), and IsoF 326 (± 2). By contrast, glutathione-dependent detoxification protein
29 329 sizes were more variable, with IsoG averaging 177 amino acids (± 6), IsoH 206 (± 7), IsoI 219 (± 18),
30 330 and IsoJ 225 (± 18). The adjacent aldehyde dehydrogenase (AldH1), was highly consistent at 499
31 331 amino acids (± 0).
32 332

33 333 Pairwise BLASTp comparisons were performed for each protein, with identity values grouped by
34 334 taxonomic comparison: Gram-positive vs. Gram-positive ($G^+ : G^+$), Gram-negative vs. Gram-negative
35 335 ($G^- : G^-$), and Gram-positive vs. Gram-negative ($G^+ : G^-$) (Table S3-S4). IsoA emerged as the most
36 336 conserved protein, with identities of 82.4–100 % ($G^+ : G^+$) and 81–100 % ($G^- : G^-$). Even across Gram
37 337 groups, conservation remained high (71.2–74.6 %), confirming its suitability as both a functional and
38 338 phylogenetic marker. In contrast, the IsoMO core β -subunit and reductase (IsoE and IsoF, respectively)
39 339 were among the least conserved, particularly in inter-group comparisons, with $G^+ : G^-$ identities of
40 340 47.3–54.1 % and 39.3–47.7 %, respectively. The detoxification enzymes IsoG, IsoH, IsoI, and IsoJ
41 341 also exhibited substantial divergence across Gram groups, with minimum inter-group identities ranging
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1 342 from 45.4 % to 58.2 %. AldH1 displayed intermediate conservation, with identities of 63.6–100 %
2 343 ($G^+ : G^+$) and 49.2–54.1 % ($G^+ : G^-$), consistent with a less central or more functionally flexible role.
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4 344

5 345 Overall, these comparisons show the center of the *iso* cluster (IsoA–C) is highly conserved across
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7 346 lineages, likely reflecting a strong purifying selection against detrimental mutations, contrasted by
8
9 347 higher variability in the detoxification module. Nucleotide-level comparisons (Table S6) mirrored
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11 348 these trends but showed greater variability, likely due to synonymous substitutions and divergence in
12 349 non-coding regions.
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14 350 15 16 351 17 352 **Phylogenetic analysis and alignment of proteins encoded by the *iso* cluster**

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19 353
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21 354 To assess whether conservation patterns across the proteins encoded within the *iso* cluster reflect
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23 355 vertical inheritance, modular evolution, or recombination, we constructed maximum likelihood
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25 356 phylogenies based on amino acid sequences from proteins IsoA–F, AldH and IsoG–J from the selected
26 357 genomes (Figures S2A–S12A). In all cases, Gram-positive (G^+) and Gram-negative (G^-) amino acid
27
28 358 sequences resolved as distinct, well-supported clades, consistent with long-term lineage-specific
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30 359 divergence, with pairwise amino acid identity values (described previously, Table S3) confirmed these
31 360 patterns, $G^+ : G^-$ comparisons consistently showing lower amino acid sequence identity than within-
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33 361 group comparisons.
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35 362
36 363 Protein analyses are summarized below, with phylogenetic trees (A), multiple sequence alignment (B),
37
38 364 and AlphaFold models (C) shown in Figures S2–S12. The supplementary notes summarise the main
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40 365 phylogenetic and amino acid sequence alignment features for each protein, with G^+ / G^- variation
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42 366 profiles highlighted and conserved motifs referenced to *Rh*. AD45 numbering from ESPript.
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44 367
45 368 Structural models generated for each IsoMO protein from both *iso*-type model organisms (*Rh*.
46
47 369 AD45, Gram-positive and *V*. WS11, Gram-negative) which consistently predicted well-conserved
48
49 370 structural scaffolds across all components (Figures S2C–S12C). Structural overlays confirmed that the
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51 371 IsoMO multicomponent core, elements $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$ (that include key α -helical and β -sheet elements) are
52 372 retained across clades. Structural variation between clades was mostly found in loop insertions,
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54 373 termini, and surface-exposed segments, particularly in detoxification and electron transfer proteins.

55 374 These results provide a consistent picture: the proteins at the center of the IsoMO (encoded by genes in
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1 375 the center of the *iso* cluster: IsoA–C) are highly conserved across all clades and retain functional
2 376 motifs essential for di-iron catalysis and subunit assembly. Accessory proteins such as IsoG–J exhibit
3
4 377 greater divergence and signs of duplication in Gram-positive taxa, while electron transfer components
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6 378 IsoD–F show intermediate variability, particularly in loop regions and termini. AldH1 appears loosely
7 379 linked, phylogenetically intermediate, and structurally conserved, possibly reflecting its more
8
9 380 peripheral role in the catabolic pathway.

14 383 **Pairwise topological comparisons between *iso* gene trees**

16 384
17 385 To quantify the degree of phylogenetic congruence among the *iso* genes, we computed pairwise
18
19 386 distances between gene trees using four metrics: normalized Robinson–Foulds (RF), weighted RF,
20
21 387 normalized subtree prune-and-regraft (SPR), and branch score distance. These metrics capture both
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23 388 topological similarity and evolutionary rate variation. We focus on amino acid–based trees (Figure
24
25 389 S13), as the nucleotide trees yielded comparable results but with greater uncertainty (Figure S14).

26 390
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28 391 Heatmaps showed the IsoMO core structural genes *isoA*, *isoB* and *isoE*, exhibited a high congruence
29
30 392 across all metrics, forming a tightly coherent cluster in both RF and SPR analyses (Figures S13 and
31 393 S15; de Oliveira Martins et al., 2016). The same can be observed between the reductase component
32
33 394 *isoF* gene and the structural gene *isoE*. In contrast, detoxification genes *isoG*, *isoH*, *isoI*, and *isoJ*
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35 395 showed higher pairwise distances, particularly in normalized RF and SPR metrics, consistent with their
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37 396 history of duplication, diversification, and modular evolution. They tend to cluster together on an MDS
38 397 map, however, probably due to similar (alternative) evolutionary trajectories (Figure S15). *aldH1* and
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40 398 particularly *isoE* consistently showed partial congruence with the IsoMO genes, supporting *aldH1*'s
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42 399 intermediate evolutionary linkage.

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45 401 Histogram distributions of RF distances (Figure S14) show how both amino acid and nucleotide
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47 402 alignment yield broadly similar tree-to-tree distance patterns across all metrics. Overall values were
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49 403 higher for nucleotide- than for amino acid–based trees, indicating slightly more diverse nucleotide-
50 404 based phylogenies. In all cases, most comparisons fall at intermediate distance values, with only a
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52 405 small number of very similar tree pairs.

1 407 These tree-based comparisons reinforce the modular organization of the *iso* cluster. The comparatively
2 408 low diversity of the monooxygenase components supports the hypothesis that the IsoMO core and the
3
4 409 detoxification module follow separate evolutionary trajectories. The intermediate positioning of *isoD*-
5 410 *F* and *aldH1* supports a mixed evolutionary trajectory, with components shaped by both functional
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7 411 linkage and independent adaptation.
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12 414 **IsoA and its phylogenetic position with reference to α -subunits of other SDIMOs**

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16 416 To place IsoA within the broader context of SDIMO diversity, we constructed a maximum-likelihood
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18 417 phylogeny using representative α -subunits from well-characterized SDIMO families, including
19 418 methane, alkene, toluene, and propane monooxygenases. IsoA sequences from all 11 isoprene-
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21 419 degrading genomes formed a monophyletic clade, distinct from other SDIMO lineages (Figure 2;
22
23 420 Supplementary Figures 16). Within the IsoA clade, Gram-positive and Gram-negative sequences
24
25 421 segregated into sister subgroups with strong bootstrap support, reflecting vertical inheritance shaped by
26 422 host taxonomy. MmoX, the α -subunit of soluble methane monooxygenase (sMMO), formed a separate
27
28 423 lineage within the tree, underscoring the evolutionary divergence between methane- and isoprene-
29
30 424 oxidizing systems. This topology supports a single IsoA lineage specialized for isoprene oxidation and
31 425 structured primarily by host phylogeny, consistent with vertical inheritance within Gram groups and
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33 426 substrate-specialized lineage separation within the SDIMO superfamily.
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38 429 **Structural comparison of IsoA and MmoX reveals conservation of important residues**

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40 430
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42 431 To investigate structural conservation between isoprene and methane monooxygenases, we aligned
43 432 IsoA models with the crystal structure of MmoX from *Methylococcus capsulatus* Bath (PDB: 1MTY;
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45 433 Rosenzweig et al., 1997). Multiple sequence alignment revealed that all six residues responsible for di-
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47 434 iron coordination in MmoX (e.g., E114, H147, E243) were conserved in IsoA (e.g., E110, H143,
48
49 435 E237), suggesting preservation of the catalytic core architecture (Figure 3; Table 2; Figures S17–S18).
50 436 The functional roles of these residues in IsoMO are putative and inferred from structural homology
51
52 437 rather than experimental verification; no site-directed mutagenesis or biochemical data currently
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54 438 confirm their activity. Nevertheless, the strong structural and sequence correspondence provides a
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1 439 compelling *in silico* framework to guide future mutagenesis and mechanistic studies of isoprene
2 440 oxidation.
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4 441
5 442 Protein structural overlays of IsoA (*Rh.* AD45) and MmoX showed high similarity in their α -helical
6 443 cores and active-site configuration (Figure 4A–C). Differences were observed in loop regions near the
7 444 substrate-binding site and at the N-/C-termini, including substitutions in residues predicted to be in line
8
9 445 with channel for entry of substrates and exit of products (e.g., Q234 in IsoA vs. E240 in MmoX),
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11 446 which may contribute to isoprene specificity. Protein structure models of IsoA achieved high overall
12 447 confidence (mean pLDDT \approx 91.8), with the α -helical core and di-iron ligating motifs resolved at very
13
14 448 high confidence (>95). Lower scores (<70) were confined to terminal extensions and surface-exposed
15
16 449 loops, consistent with their structural variability. Predicted alignment error (PAE) values were
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18 450 uniformly low within the catalytic core, supporting the reliability of the structural comparison with
19 451 MmoX. Together, these features indicate that IsoA retains the hallmark SDIMO fold and di-iron
20
21 452 catalytic geometry while exhibiting clade-specific divergence in substrate-binding regions.
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28 455 **IsoA dimer modeling and clade-specific conservation**

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31 457 Multimer predictions for IsoA from *Rh.* AD45 and *V.* WS11 yielded stable dimeric assemblies with
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33 458 symmetric head-to-tail arrangements. The predicted interface was dominated by conserved α -helical
34
35 459 contacts, and the overall fold was highly consistent across both clades (Figure S19). Structural
36
37 460 superposition of the two dimer models showed near-complete alignment of core helices and di-iron-
38 461 binding residues, with minor differences restricted to loop extensions and termini. Model confidence
39
40 462 was high, with the *Rh.* AD45 IsoA dimer achieving a mean pLDDT of 90.8 (median 95.4), with over
41
42 463 80% of residues scoring above 90. Predicted template modeling scores (pTM = 0.86) and interface
43 464 scores (ipTM = 0.83) supported a reliable dimer arrangement. Predicted alignment error (PAE) values
44
45 465 were low within monomers (mean ~ 6 Å) and moderate at the interface (median ~ 8.3 Å), consistent
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47 466 with confident core contacts and some flexibility in loop regions. Together, these results suggest that
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49 467 IsoA dimerization is a structurally conserved feature of IsoMO systems and likely critical for
50 468 maintaining the catalytic configuration across diverse isoprene degraders.
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55 471 **Structural modelling of the IsoMO putative catalytic core**

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1
2 473 AlphaFold3 multimer predictions for the IsoMO from *Rh. AD45* recovered the expected $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$ IsoMO
3
4 474 core assembly comprising two IsoA (α ; cyan), two IsoE (β ; purple), and two IsoB (γ ; green) subunits
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6 475 (Figure 5). Conserved α -helical bundles within IsoA form the di-iron active site, while the β - and γ -
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8 476 subunits provide peripheral stabilising contacts consistent with the SDIMO. The IsoMO core was
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10 477 modelled with high global and interface confidence (pTM = 0.88; ipTM = 0.86 for *Rh. AD45*),
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12 478 indicating a reliable subunit orientation and well-defined assembly interface (Abramson et al., 2024,
13
14 479 Jumper et al., 2021). Residue-level confidence was also high for conserved regions (pLDDT > 90),
15
16 480 confirming a robustly folded catalytic scaffold. Lower scores (<50) were limited to short terminal or
17
18 481 surface-exposed regions, consistent with expected flexibility in non-core segments.

19 482
19 483 Structural superposition of the IsoMO core with the sMMO hydroxylase from *Methylococcus*
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21 484 *capsulatus* Bath (PDB: 1MTY) revealed strong overall correspondence specifically between the $\alpha_2\beta_2$
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23 485 architectures, including alignment of conserved α -helical bundles and di-iron centres (Figure S20, refer
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25 486 to IsoA residues in Figure 4). Together, these results provide a high-confidence structural framework
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27 487 for the IsoMO core.

488 **Discussion**

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6 490 This study used isolate-based genomic and structural comparison analyses to investigate the evolution
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8 491 and function of IsoMO across diverse bacterial taxa. By addressing key questions in microbial ecology
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10 492 (Antwis et al., 2017), we provide insights into microbial evolutionary processes and functional
11 493 diversity underlying isoprene degradation. Protein phylogenetic and comparative genomic analysis
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13 494 support strong conservation of the IsoMO catalytic core alongside lineage-specific variation in
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15 495 accessory and detoxification genes. Together, these patterns support the view that IsoMO is maintained
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17 496 as a vertically inherited, functionally constrained enzymatic module, with surrounding regulatory and
18 497 redox components exhibiting greater evolutionary flexibility, potentially in response to host-specific
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20 498 ecological and physiological pressures.

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23 499 Structural modelling reinforces this interpretation. Despite sequence divergence between Gram-
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25 500 positive and Gram-negative taxa, the IsoMO core retains a conserved multicomponent architecture
26 501 characteristic of Group1 soluble di-iron monooxygenases. IsoA carries a highly conserved di-iron
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28 502 center closely resembling MmoX (Rosenzweig et al. 1997). This structural continuity supports the
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30 503 view that sMMO and IsoMO arose either from a shared ancestral monooxygenase, as suggested by
31 504 Leahy (2003), or evolutionary convergence, with both enzymes subsequently adapting to distinct
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33 505 carbon substrates. IsoA was consistently the most conserved subunit, supporting its role as the
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35 506 evolutionary anchor of the *iso* cluster and the principal determinant of isoprene oxidation (Carrion et
36
37 507 al., 2018, Crombie et al., 2015). Substrate-channel differences relative to MmoX (e.g., G208, C151,
38 508 M184, E240 versus V202, D147, V178, Q234) may underpin isoprene specificity (Merkx et al., 2001;
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40 509 Borodina et al., 2007) and provide a framework for targeted mutagenesis and mechanistic studies.

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43 510 From an ecological perspective, this modular organization may facilitate its persistence across diverse
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45 511 environments and host taxa. Isoprene-degrading and methane-oxidising bacteria have been reported in
46 512 plant-associated habitats such as the phyllosphere of *Sphagnum* moss (e.g. *Methylocella* spp., Dedysch
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48 513 et al. 2005; Crombie et al., 2025). Because *Sphagnum* hosts active degraders of both methane and
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50 514 isoprene, it represents a natural environment in which the evolutionary history of these
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52 515 monooxygenases may converge at the interphase between aerial and submerged tissue, supporting the
53 516 analysis and comparison of IsoA to MmoX and for exploring how related monooxygenases contribute
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55 517 to carbon cycling.

1 518 Within this ecological context, genomic and functional patterns may also help explain observations
2 519 from microcosm studies. In *Sphagnum* moss, isoprene degradation was inhibited by 1-octyne but not
3
4 520 by acetylene (Crombie et al., 2025; Dawson et al., 2020), consistent with a target within the conserved
5 521 IsoMO active site. Structural models therefore provide a framework for interpreting such inhibition
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7 522 and for developing future imaging or probe-based approaches to study IsoMO activity *in situ*. Future
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9 523 studies should examine how substrates and inhibitors interact with IsoMO at the structural and
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11 524 molecular level, how variation in these interactions influences the microbial community adaptation and
12 525 plant–microbiome interactions under environmental change.
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15 526 Beyond these ecological implications, our phylogenetic analyses also help clarify long-standing
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17 527 misannotation issues, which likely arise from the limited representation of verified *iso* cluster
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19 528 sequences in public databases (Dawson et al., 2023). Moving forward, a combined strategy that
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21 529 couples direct phenotypic assays with indirect, sequence-based inference of active *iso*-type degraders
22 530 (Larke-Mejía et al., 2019; Ledford et al., 2025) will be essential for improving database accuracy and
23
24 531 strengthening ecological and evolutionary analyses. IsoA grouped closely with TmoA- and XamoA-
25
26 532 like α -subunits (Dawson et al., 2020), indicating that further comparative work on these related
27 533 SDIMOs will be essential for identifying residues that differentiate substrate selection across isoprene-,
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29 534 toluene-, and alkene-oxidizing enzymes.
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31

32 535 Overall, these structural and genomic insights highlight that IsoMO represents a conserved and stable
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34 536 microbial function with direct ecological significance. Because isoprene degradation is the only known
35
36 537 biological sink of one of the most abundantly produced biogenic volatile organic compounds,
37 538 understanding the evolutionary stability and mechanistic basis of IsoMO may be critical for predicting
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39 539 how microbial communities influence isoprene fluxes, plant–microbe interactions and VOC-driven
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41 540 ecosystem processes.
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45 542 **Conclusions**

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49 544 This study presents an integrated evolutionary and structural analysis of isoprene monooxygenase
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51 545 (IsoMO) from confirmed isoprene-degrading isolates. We demonstrate that IsoMO comprises a highly
52 546 conserved $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$ di-iron monooxygenase core, closely related to the soluble methane monooxygenase
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54 547 hydroxylase, embedded within a more flexible accessory framework. This organisation supports a
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56 548 model in which the *iso* gene cluster combines vertical inheritance of a functionally constrained
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1 549 catalytic unit with adaptive diversification of auxiliary components. By establishing a deep structural
2 550 and evolutionary relationship between IsoMO and other soluble di-iron monooxygenases, this work
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4 551 reveals that the enzymatic machinery responsible for oxidising two of Earth's most abundant biogenic
5 552 volatile organic compounds (methane and isoprene) shares a conserved catalytic framework that has
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7 553 diversified to support contrasting ecological roles. The strong conservation of IsoA further supports its
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9 554 use as a reliable molecular marker for isoprene degradation and for identifying active isoprene-
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11 555 degrading populations in environmental studied. Future work should prioritize isolation and
12 556 experimental validation of predicted IsoMO complexes and structure-guided inhibitor interactions.
13
14 557 Integrating structural insights with inhibitor-based imaging, microcosm, and mesocosm studies will
15
16 558 improve understandind of microbial communities influence VOC fluxes under changing environmental
17
18 559 conditions.

22 562 **Funding**

24 563
26 564 This work was supported by the European Union through a Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions
27
28 565 Independent Fellowship [grant number 101150622— u-Arctic] to **N.L.L.M.** and European Research
29
30 566 Council Advanced Grant [grant number 694578—IsoMet] to **J.C.M. L.d.O.M.** was supported by the
31 567 UK Office for Life Sciences (OLS) through funding provided to the North West sub-national Secure
32
33 568 Data Environment (NW SDE) and to the Cheshire and Merseyside Integrated Care Board (CM ICB).
34
35 569 Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the
36
37 570 European Union or the Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting
38 571 authority can be held responsible for them.
39

43 574 **Acknowledgements**

45 575
47 576 This project was supported by The Danish National Research Foundation within the Center for
48
49 577 Volatile Interactions (VOLT, DNRF168). We would also like to acknowledge Laura Martinez Alvarez
50 578 and Mario Rodriguez Mestre (University of Copenhagen) for insights into structural models with
51
52 579 AlphaFold. Artificial intelligence (AI) was used to interpret some of the AlphaFold outputs and
53
54 580 improve the clarity of the discussion in the second rebuttal.
55
56 581

582

Authors contributions

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585 **Nasmille L. Larke-Mejía:** Conceptualization (equal), Methodology (lead), Formal analysis (lead),
586 Writing – original draft preparation (lead), Writing-Review and Editing (lead), Funding acquisition
587 (equal). **J. Colin Murrell:** Conceptualization (equal), Writing-Review and Editing (equal), Funding
588 acquisition (equal). **Leonardo de Oliveira Martins:** Formal analysis (phylogenetic congruence),
589 Writing-Review and Editing (limited contribution).

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Data availability

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594 The data underlying this article are available in ERDA at <https://sid.erda.dk/sharelink/CY7eSNcgUJ>.

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Figure 1. Organization of the *iso* gene clusters in 11 representative isoprene-degrading bacteria. *iso* clusters containing the *isoA* gene and associated operon components were extracted from annotated genomes. Homologous genes across strains are connected by grey links, with shading indicating amino acid identity (threshold: $\geq 20\%$). Genes are coloured and labelled according to putative functions: *isoA–isoJ* encode the isoprene monooxygenase complex (including the center of the cluster *isoA–C*) and associated electron transfer proteins; *aldH1/2*, *gshA/B*, *gorA*, *marR*, and *lysR* represent adjacent genes putatively involved in regulation, redox processes, or glutathione metabolism. Strain names are shown on the left, with clusters scaled proportionally. Gene orientations reflect native operon direction. In Gram-positive strains, most *Rhodococcus* genomes harboured duplicated *isoGHIJ* modules flanking the monooxygenase genes, whereas Gram-negative strains showed a single contiguous operon. Notably, *Rh. WS1* lacked the duplicated detoxification module, retaining only a single *isoGHIJ* copy, suggesting intra-lineage structural variability.

Figure 2. SDIMO α -subunit phylogeny and placement of IsoA. Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of soluble di-iron monooxygenase (SDIMO) α -subunits showing the placement of IsoA sequences from 11 confirmed isoprene degraders (Gram-positive and Gram-negative) relative to representative SDIMO groups. One to two representative sequences were retained per major SDIMO lineage (BmoX, PrmA, ThmA, TmoA) and six MmoX sequences, together with all IsoA sequences included in this study. IsoA forms a distinct, well-supported clade separated into Gram-positive (*Rhodococcus*, *Gordonia*, *Mycobacterium*, *Nocardioides*) and Gram-negative (*Variovorax*, *Sphingopyxis*, *Ramlibacter*) subclades. The analytical procedure encompassed 29 amino acid sequences with 617 positions in the final dataset. Scale bar represents amino acid substitutions per site. Accession numbers and full taxa are provided in Supplementary Table 5.

Figure 3. Protein sequence comparison of isoprene monooxygenase α -subunit (IsoA) and soluble methane monooxygenase α -subunit (MmoX). Multiple sequence alignment of MmoX and IsoA α -subunits visualised with ESPript 3.0, using *Rh. AD45* IsoA as the structural reference for residue numbering and secondary structure annotation. Arrows indicate known or putative features of IsoA/MmoX (1) iron binding ligand residue in red, (2) implicated in methane oxidation in blue, (3) gating residue in black, (4) residues which might confer enantioselectivity in oxidation products in dark green, (5) highly conserved residue in orange, (6) hydrogen bonding (C-F helices) in grey, (7) delivery of electrons to the active site in purple, (8) tightly packed regions in brown, (9) canyon residues for protein B or oxidoreductase, (10) handle residues in light green, (11) important docking residues in teal and the letter D, and (12) residues that interacts with the gamma subunit in pink, according to Leahy *et al* (Table 2). Abbreviations of the annotated residues: H, hydrophobic residues surrounding the diiron center; S, structural residues involved in hydrogen bonding of the alpha-helices A and C; *, iron cluster ligands; D, docking residues; Fe(A), iron cluster ligands for Fe(A) iron center; Fe(B), iron cluster ligands for Fe(B) iron center. Other labels describe the location or possible function of the residue.

Figure 4. Structural comparison of IsoA and MmoX α -subunits. Two views of the cartoon representation of the α -subunit of isoprene monooxygenase (IsoA, *Rh. AD45*, cyan) predicted by AlphaFold2 and the α -subunit of soluble methane monooxygenase (MmoX, *Methylococcus capsulatus* Bath, PDB: 1MTY, blue) superimposed and visualised in PyMOL. Residues involved in iron coordination (IsoA in pink, MmoX in orange) and active site channel (IsoA in purple, MmoX in green) are highlighted in ribbon representation and detail annotated with residue type and position for MmoX (F4C). Location of iron atoms (red spheres in F4B, red FE in F4C) are shown in reference to sMMO in SF17 and the sMMO from 1MTY PDB model. Two magnifications and slight changes in orientation of the active site are shown to illustrate the conservation of the non-heme di-iron catalytic core and surrounding helices. The figure highlights both the conserved channel residues (TN) and EXXH motifs along with clade-specific substitutions near the active site, consistent with shared SDIMO ancestry but functional divergence for isoprene oxidation. Mean pLDDT give an overall confidence score of ~ 91.8 .

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3 **Figure 5. Predicted architecture of the IsoMO catalytic core.** Two views of the quaternary structure of the
4 isoprene monooxygenase (IsoMO) hydroxylase core from *Rh. AD45*. Multimer recovered the expected $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$
5 oxygenase assembly, comprising an IsoA dimer (cyan), two IsoE subunits (purple), and two IsoB subunits
6 (green), closely resembling the architecture of other soluble di-iron monooxygenase (SDIMO) hydroxylases.
7 Model confidence was very high overall with most residues scoring above 90. The core fold was strongly
8 supported (pTM = 0.89), while inter-subunit interfaces showed high confidence (ipTM = 0.86), consistent with
9 a stable, well-defined catalytic assembly and limited flexibility in peripheral contact regions.
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Table 1. Summary of all reported *iso*-type bacterial genomes. These isolates include confirmed and putative isoprene degraders from diverse habitats. Plant hosts are listed where known. The 11 genomes included in the main figures of this study are denoted by an asterisk (*). Sequences suppressed in GenBank due to genome size (#). All eleven sequences were included in supplementary analyses. Genome size and protein-coding gene count were obtained from NCBI assembly records.

Class	Isolate	Assembly accession	Reference	Source	Plant Host	Genome size (Mb)	Protein-coding genes
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Rhodococcus</i> AD45 *	ASM94930v1 (Mar 2015)	(van Hylckama Vlieg <i>et al.</i> 1998)	freshwater	N/A	6.79479	6029
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Rhodococcus opacus</i> PD630 *	ASM23433v1 (Nov 2011)	(Alvarez <i>et al.</i> 1996; Crombie <i>et al.</i> 2015)	soil	N/A	9.16903	8942
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Rhodococcus</i> LB1	ASM158345v1 (Mar 2016)	(El Khawand <i>et al.</i> 2016)	leaf	<i>A. hippocastanum</i>	10.752	9270
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Rhodococcus</i> SC4 #	ASM155547v1 (Mar 2016)	(El Khawand <i>et al.</i> 2016)	soil	N/A	10.5719	9123
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Rhodococcus</i> ACPA1 *	ASM230019v1 (Sept 2017)	(Crombie <i>et al.</i> 2017, 2018)	leaf	<i>Populus alba</i>	10.0608	8808
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Rhodococcus</i> ACPA4	ASM230018v1 (Sept 2017)	(Crombie <i>et al.</i> 2017, 2018)	leaf	<i>Populus alba</i>	7.06712	6247
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Rhodococcus</i> ACS1	ASM230015v1 (Sept 2017)	(Crombie <i>et al.</i> 2017, 2018)	soil	<i>Salix fragilis</i>	10.8914	9508
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Rhodococcus</i> WS1 *	ASM379774v1 (Nov 2018)	(Larke-Mejia 2018)	soil	<i>Salix alba</i>	6.56024	5943
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Rhodococcus</i> WS3	ASM379708v1 (Nov 2018)	(Larke-Mejia <i>et al.</i> 2019)	soil	<i>Salix alba</i>	6.85616	6095
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Rhodococcus</i> WS4 #	ASM654360v1 (July 2019)	(Larke-Mejia <i>et al.</i> 2019)	soil	<i>Salix alba</i>	12.7295	10854
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Rhodococcus</i> WS7	ASM654361v1 (July 2019)	(Larke-Mejia <i>et al.</i> 2019)	soil	<i>Salix alba</i>	6.6282	6053
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Gordonia</i> i37 *	ASM204308v1 (Mar 2017)	(Acuña Alvarez <i>et al.</i> 2009; Johnston <i>et al.</i> 2017)	estuary	N/A	6.22816	5486
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Gordonia</i> OPL2 *	ASM379782v1 (Nov 2018)	(Larke-Mejia <i>et al.</i> 2020)	leaf	<i>E. guineensis</i>	5.7959	5169
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Mycobacterium</i> AT1 *	ASM204309v1 (Mar 2017)	(Johnston <i>et al.</i> 2017)	estuary	N/A	7.07238	6620
<i>Actinomycetes</i>	<i>Nocardioides</i> WS12 *	ASM1410886v1 (Aug 2020)	(Larke-Mejia <i>et al.</i> 2019; Gibson, Larke-Mejia and Murrell 2020)	soil	<i>Salix alba</i>	5.17107	4925
<i>Betaproteobacteria</i>	<i>Ramlibacter</i> WS9 *	ASM379776v1 (Nov 2018)	(Larke-Mejia <i>et al.</i> 2019)	soil	<i>Salix alba</i>	6.98085	6517
<i>Betaproteobacteria</i>	<i>Variovorax</i> WS11 *	ASM1049924v1 (Mar2018) ASM301487v1 (Feb2020)	(Crombie <i>et al.</i> 2018; Larke-Mejia <i>et al.</i> 2019; Carrión <i>et al.</i> 2020)	soil	<i>Salix alba</i>	8.48961	7789
<i>Alphaproteobacteria</i>	<i>Sphingopyxis</i> OPL5 *	ASM379777v2 (Sept 2020)	(Larke-Mejia <i>et al.</i> 2019, 2020)	leaf	<i>E. guineensis</i>	4.67697	4418

Table 2. Functionally important residues in MmoX vs. IsoA, mapped according to *Methylosinus trichosporium* Ob3b (MmoX) and *Rhodococcus* sp. AD45 (IsoA) sequence numbering. **Note:** The functional roles of IsoA residues are putative, based solely on in silico structural and sequence homology with MmoX (PDB 1MTY). These predicted correspondences identify candidate positions for future site-directed mutagenesis to verify catalytic and structural roles within the IsoMO di-iron centre.

Residue function	MmoX	IsoA
Gating	L110	L101
Enantioselectivity	G113, G208	G104, V202
Important in methane oxidation	C151, M184, F282	D147, V178, F274
Highly conserved	T213	T207
Iron ligand	E114, E144, H147, E209, E243, H246	E110, E140, H143, E203, E237, H240
Hydrogen bonding between C and F helices	D143, R146, S238, D242, R245	D139, R142, S232, D236, R239
Access of substrates and release of products to and from the active site	T213, N214, E240	T207, N208, Q234
tightly packed regions of the protein canyon	A117, G250	A113, G244
handle	Y67, K74, L321, G325, P329	Y64, K71, G315, P319
possible docking	A224, G228, D229	A218, G222, D223
interact with gamma	Y292, W371, Y376, P377	Y284, W362, Y367, P368
	P424, G443, P461, Y464	P408, G427, Y430

1 **Structural and evolutionary insights into the isoprene monooxygenases**

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4 3 Larke-Mejía, N.L.^{a, b*}, de Oliveira Martins, L.^c and Murrell, J.C.^b

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6
7 5 ^aCenter for Volatile Interactions (VOLT), Department of Biology, University of Copenhagen,
8
9 6 Universitetsparken 15, Copenhagen Ø, 2100, Denmark.

10
11 7 ^bSchool of Environmental Sciences, University of East Anglia, Norwich, NR4 7TJ, UK.

12
13 8 ^cSignal Processing Group, Dept Electrical Engineering and Electronics, University of Liverpool, L69
14 9 7ZF, Liverpool, UK.

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42 25 ***Corresponding author:**

43 26 Nasmille L. Larke-Mejía

44
45 27 Email: nala@bio.ku.dk

46
47 28 Center for Volatile Interactions (VOLT), Department of Biology, University of Copenhagen,
48
49 29 Universitetsparken 15, Copenhagen Ø, 2100, Denmark

50 30 VOLT mobile number: +45 23 84 00 79

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Abstract

Isoprene, a highly reactive biogenic volatile organic compound (VOC) emitted by terrestrial vegetation, influences atmospheric chemistry but its microbial degradation remains poorly understood. Aerobic degradation begins with isoprene monooxygenase (IsoMO), a multicomponent di-iron monooxygenase encoded by the *isoABCDEF* cluster, with *isoGHIJ* supporting downstream steps. We analysed *iso* gene clusters from eleven confirmed isoprene degraders, reconstructed amino acid sequence phylogenies and generated structural models of IsoMO components using mainly AlphaFold2. IsoA, IsoE, and IsoB formed a highly conserved $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$ monooxygenase core (IsoMO core) whose predicted architecture and closely resembled the soluble methane monooxygenase (sMMO) hydroxylase, revealing a shared di-iron catalytic framework adapted to distinct hydrocarbon substrates. IsoA was the most conserved subunit and remains a reliable molecular marker for isoprene degradation. This work presents the first detailed structural model of an IsoMO core and reveals its deep relationship to other soluble di-iron monooxygenases. Together these results provide a molecular foundation for future mechanistic, ecological and inhibitor-based studies linking enzyme-level specificity to microbial control of isoprene turnover under changing climate conditions.

Keywords: isoprene degradation, isoprene monooxygenase, IsoA, soluble di-iron monooxygenase, methane monooxygenase, protein sequence evolution, structural modelling, functional marker genes

50 Introduction

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53 Isoprene (2-methyl-1,3-butadiene) is a highly reactive C₅ hydrocarbon and the most abundantly
54 emitted non-methane biogenic volatile organic compound (BVOC), released primarily by terrestrial
55 plants, with global emissions comparable to methane at rates exceeding ~ 500 Tg per year (Guenther et
56 al., 2012; reviewed in Carrión et al., 2020). In the atmosphere, isoprene plays a major role in the
57 formation of tropospheric ozone and secondary organic aerosols (SOAs), which impact air quality,
58 cloud properties, and radiative forcing (Claeys et al., 2004; Wennberg et al., 2018; Shen et al., 2024).
59 While its atmospheric chemistry is well characterized, microbial degradation of isoprene is a new
60 research area (reviewed in Dawson et al., 2023).

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62 Recent evidence has shown that bacteria from diverse environments (soil, aquatic and leaf surfaces)
63 can degrade isoprene, making microbial degradation the only known biological sink of atmospheric
64 isoprene (McGenity et al., 2018; Carrión et al., 2020). In some ecosystems, such as *Sphagnum*-
65 dominated peatlands, microbial uptake of isoprene may even counterbalance net emissions from the
66 moss (Crombie et al., 2025).

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68 Aerobic isoprene degradation (*iso*-type, Figure S1) is initiated by isoprene monooxygenase (IsoMO)
69 encoded by the *isoABCDEF* genes. IsoMO is a multicomponent di-iron monooxygenase enzyme from
70 Group 1 of the soluble di-iron centre monooxygenase family (SDIMO) essential for the first step of
71 isoprene degradation (Crombie et al., 2015; Dawson et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2025). This
72 monooxygenation step yields (R)-epoxyisoprene (van Hylckama Vlieg et al., 2000), a toxic
73 intermediate which is further processed and detoxified via a glutathione-dependent pathway encoded
74 by *isoGHIJ* (Rix et al., 2023). The core *iso* gene cluster (*iso* cluster) typically comprises 11 genes
75 (*isoA-isoJ*, *aldH*) (Dawson et al., 2023). Within IsoMO monooxygenase core (IsoMO core: $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$;
76 Zhou et al. 1998; Leahy et al. 2003), IsoA encodes the central catalytic α -subunit component, which
77 contains a di-iron active site (van Hylckama Vlieg et al., 1998) and IsoE and IsoB encode the
78 associated β -subunit and γ -subunits, respectively (van Hylckama Vlieg et al., 2000). The IsoMO also
79 contains IsoC (a Rieske-type ferredoxin), IsoD (a coupling protein), and IsoF (an FMN-containing
80 reductase component) that extract electrons from NADH and transfers them to the di-iron center in the
81 monooxygenase α -subunit (Zhou et al., 1998; van Hylckama Vlieg et al., 2000), as seen with other

82 SDIMO such as methane and toluene monooxygenases (Rosenzweig et al., 1997; Notomista et al.,
83 2003; Wang et al., 2014).

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85 The detoxification module pathway includes first IsoI, an isoprene pathway-specific glutathione S-
86 transferase (GST) (van Hylckama Vlieg et al., 1998; Van Hylckama Vlieg et al., 1999), which
87 conjugates epoxyisoprene with glutathione (GSH) to produce HGMB (1-hydroxy-2-glutathionyl-2-
88 methyl-3-butene) (Rix et al., 2023). IsoH (an NAD⁺-dependent dehydrogenase) which sequentially
89 oxidizes HGMB in two NAD⁺-dependent steps to form GMBA (2-glutathionyl-2-methyl-3-butanoic
90 acid) (Rix et al., 2023). IsoG (a putative CoA-transferase) then converts GMBA into GMBA-CoA by
91 attaching coenzyme A (from an unknown source). In the same step IsoJ, encodes for the second
92 isoprene pathway-specific GST assigned to the Actino-like class of GST (Haarmann et al., 2025), that
93 removes oxidized glutathione (GSSG) from GMBA-CoA, producing MBE-CoA (2-methyl-3-hydroxy-
94 butenyl-CoA, Dawson et al., 2022; Rix et al., 2023). The final gene in the cluster is *aldH* which
95 encodes a putative aldehyde dehydrogenase thought to oxidize intermediates of HGMB to GMBA
96 (Dawson et al., 2022) and likely catalyzes a second NAD⁺-dependent oxidation step as in the
97 StyH/AldH1 system of styrene metabolism (Dawson et al., 2023; Rix et al., 2023).

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99 Within the *iso* cluster, *isoA* is the most conserved gene and has been widely used as a molecular
100 marker for detecting and anchoring *iso* cluster genes from isoprene degraders detected in
101 environmental DNA using PCR and qPCR assays and metagenomics (El Khawand et al., 2016; Larke-
102 Mejía et al., 2019; Carrión et al., 2020). IsoA shares ancestry with MmoX (Group 3 SDIMO, Yang et
103 al., 2025), the catalytic α -subunit of soluble methane monooxygenase (sMMO), and with the toluene
104 and alkene monooxygenases (Leahy et al., 2003; Coleman et al., 2006; McGenity et al., 2018).
105 Although sMMO has been thoroughly characterized (Rosenzweig et al., 1993; Hakemian and
106 Rosenzweig, 2007), detailed structural insights into IsoA are lacking.

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108 *Iso*-type degraders have been isolated from a wide range of environments yet the evolutionary history,
109 modular organization, and structure-to-function relationships of the *iso* cluster are poorly understood
110 and no systematic phylogenetic or structural comparison of the proteins encoded in the full *isoA-J*,
111 *aldH* cluster has been performed. Also, the evolutionary congruence of individual proteins, patterns of
112 duplication within the gene cluster, and the structural similarity of IsoA to other SDIMO α -subunits
113 remain unexplored. To address this, we conducted a comparative genomic and structural analysis of
114 the *iso* cluster in confirmed *iso*-type isoprene-degrading bacteria. Our aims were to: (i) visualise the

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1 115 gene order and modular structure of the core *iso* cluster; (ii) construct nucleotide and protein
2 116 phylogenies to evaluate evolutionary congruence across the cluster; (iii) compare IsoA to
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4 117 representative SDIMO α -subunits to identify conserved functional motifs; and (iv) use AlphaFold2
5 118 monomer and multimer modelling and structural alignment to explore IsoA structure and active site
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7 119 architecture.
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11 121 Anchored by the well-characterized sMMO framework, this study places IsoMO within the broader
12 122 evolutionary landscape of microbial one-carbon (C₁) and hydrocarbon monooxygenases. Our
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14 123 integrated approach provides the first detailed structural and phylogenetic comparison of IsoA with
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16 124 MmoX and lays the groundwork for future biochemical and ecological studies of isoprene metabolism.
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18 125 We hypothesized that: (i) phylogenetic signals within the *iso* cluster reflect vertical inheritance with
19 126 taxon-specific modularity; (ii) IsoA is the most conserved and functionally constrained gene within the
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21 127 cluster, with structural features similar to MmoX; and (iii) IsoA and MmoX share conserved catalytic
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23 128 residues, reflecting mechanistic parallels in hydrocarbon oxidation.
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129 **Methods**

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132 *Genome selection and dataset compilation*

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134 18 bacterial genomes representing extant *iso*-type isoprene-degrading strains were identified, 15 Gram-
135 positive strains, primarily from the genus *Rhodococcus* (e.g., *Rh.* AD45, *Rh. opacus* PD630, *Rh.* LB1,
136 *Rh.* WS7), two *Gordonia* (*Gordonia* sp. i37 and *Gordonia* sp. OPL2), *Mycobacterium* sp. AT1, and
137 *Nocardioides* sp. WS12 plus three Gram-negative representatives of the Comamonadaceae family
138 (*Ramlibacter* sp. WS9, *Variovorax* sp. WS11, and *Sphingopyxis* sp. OPL5). From this dataset, 11
139 genomes were selected for downstream analyses based on published reports of isoprene catabolism,
140 active enrichment in DNA-SIP experiments, and the presence of key catabolic genes, such as *isoA*.
141 Assembly statistics (e.g., N50, L50, genome size, GC content, and supporting references) are provided
142 in Table S1. These 11 isolates also represent phylogenetic breadth, ecological diversity (soil,
143 freshwater, and phyllosphere origins), and known variation in *iso* cluster structure (Table 1).

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146 *Identification and extraction of isoprene metabolic gene clusters*

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148 Gene clusters were identified in the genomes of 11 isoprene-degrading bacterial isolates. Genomic
149 assemblies were obtained in FASTA format (.fna) from NCBI or locally-generated assemblies. Initial
150 cluster coordinates were based on the NCBI GenBank public annotation and homology to known *isoA*-
151 containing regions. Where required, complete contigs were searched using BLAST to identify the
152 location of *isoA* homologues. To validate and refine cluster extraction, an IsoA protein sequence
153 database was used as a query in a tblastn search against all genome contigs. Each genome was split
154 into individual contig files using Biopython (Cock et al., 2009) and combined into a single nucleotide
155 BLAST database using makeblastdb (NCBI BLAST+ suite v 2.12.0+, (Camacho et al., 2009)).
156 Matching contigs were filtered to retain the top-scoring *isoA*-containing regions, and from these
157 contigs the whole identifiable *iso* operon was extracted with an additional ± 2 kb of flanking sequence
158 at each side of the operon (total region varied from 13kb to 29kb between isolates) and stored in a
159 curated directory. Where needed, specific contigs from GenBank (e.g., NZ_RKME01000032.1 for
160 *Gordonia* sp. OPL2) were targeted to extract the correct cluster. During trimming, GenBank records

1 161 were validated to retain the molecule_type annotation and any features located entirely within the
2 162 extracted region were retained and coordinate-shifted accordingly.
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7 165 *Functional annotation, visualization and comparative analysis*

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11 167 All curated *isoA* cluster regions were re-annotated using Bakta (v1.11.4, (Schwengers et al. 2021)
12 168 against the full Bakta reference database (Zenodo, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7997310). Annotated .gbk
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14 169 files for each *iso* cluster were then visualized in Figure 1 and compared across the 11 isoprene-
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16 170 degrading isolates using Clinker (v0.0.31; Gilchrist and Chooi, 2021). Where necessary, whole cluster
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18 171 orientation and gene labels were manually curated to improve interpretability.
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23 174 *iso cluster identification and comparative genomics*

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26 176 The 11 *iso* genes (*isoA-J*, *aldH*, referred to here collectively as the 11 *iso* genes) were identified in the
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28 177 selected genomes and cluster boundaries were defined by syntenic neighborhood, proximity, and
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30 178 functional annotations. Protein and nucleotide sequences were extracted for each gene and compiled
31 179 into FASTA files for further analysis (Table S2).
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35 181 Pairwise sequence similarity was assessed using BLASTn (nucleotide) and BLASTp (protein) with
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37 182 default parameters. Percent identity matrices were generated for each gene (protein: Table S3) and
38 183 mean pairwise identity values were computed and grouped by Gram type (Gram+:Gram+, Gram-
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40 184 :Gram-, Gram+:Gram-), to quantify taxonomic divergence (Table S4).
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45 187 *Phylogenetic and sequence alignment analyses*

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48 189 DNA and predicted amino acid sequences for the 11 *iso* cluster genes from each of the 11 genomes
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50 190 (Table 1) were used to infer gene-by-gene phylogenies. Multiple sequence protein alignment was
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52 191 generated using MAFFT v7.505 (Kato and Standley, 2013) with the L-INS-i strategy and trimmed
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54 192 with trimAl v1.4 (Capella-Gutiérrez et al., 2009) using the auto mode. For each full protein alignment,
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56 193 maximum likelihood phylogenetic trees (Figures S2A–S12A) were constructed with IQTREE2 v2.4.0
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1 194 (Minh et al., 2020) under an LG evolutionary model (Le and Gascuel, 2008) with gamma
2 195 heterogeneity (Yang, 1994). Branching support was assessed with 10,000 ultrafast bootstrap replicates
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4 196 as implemented in IQTREE2 (Hoang et al., 2018), where the best tree as well as each bootstrap
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6 197 replicate were further optimised using a nearest neighbor interchange search. The same procedure was
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8 198 used for the DNA alignment, under an HKY model (Hasegawa et al., 1985) with gamma heterogeneity
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10 199 (Yang, 1994).

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12 201 For visualisation and protein structure prediction purposes, the alignment was visualised with ESPript
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14 202 3.0 (Robert and Gouet, 2014) (Figures S2B–S12B) with secondary structure elements annotated using
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16 203 *Rh* sp. AD45 as a reference for numbering. Conserved sequence motifs characteristic of di-iron
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18 204 monooxygenases motifs were identified manually and verified using UniProt (UniProt Consortium,
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20 205 2025) and PDB annotations (Zardecki et al., 2022).

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23 207 To assess phylogenetic congruence among genes and input data source, normalised tree distances
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25 208 between all maximum likelihood tree pairs were calculated, including comparisons between amino
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27 209 acid-derived and nucleotide-derived trees. For these calculations, the phangorn library for R was used
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29 210 (Schliep, 2011). Specifically, we calculated four distances between all tree pairs: the Robinson Foulds
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31 211 (RF) (Robinson and Foulds, 1981) and the subtree prune and regraft (SPR) (de Oliveira Martins et al.,
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33 212 2008) normalised by their maximum values. These distances only take the topologies into account, and
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35 213 therefore to account also for branch lengths, we employed the weighted RF (Robinson and Foulds,
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37 214 1979) and the branch score distances (Kuhner and Felsenstein, 1984) on rescaled branch lengths, so
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39 215 that trees had comparable phylogenetic diversity. All distances were visualised as a heatmap to
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41 216 highlight clusters of phylogenetically similar histories and congruent genes, and their distribution was
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43 217 summarised in a histogram to assess the degree of overall topological similarity. Multidimensional
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45 218 scaling (MDS) was applied to the distance matrices using the cmdscale function in R v4.3.1 to project
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47 219 relationships among gene trees into two-dimensions, enabling visual detection of phylogenetically
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49 220 coherent gene modules. Figures were generated using ggplot2 v3.4.2 and ggtree (Yu et al., 2017) in R,
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51 221 and for visualisation purposes the trees were re-rooted by midpoint rooting using the phangorn library
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53 222 (Schliep, 2011).

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56 225 *Structural modelling of IsoMO subunits and complexes*

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227 Protein structure predictions were performed using AlphaFold2 implemented in ColabFold v1.5.2
228 (Mirdita et al., 2022), which integrates MMseqs2-based multiple sequence alignment (Steinegger and
229 Söding, 2017) and the AlphaFold2 inference pipeline (Jumper et al. 2021), using default parameters.
230 For each of the 11 genes, monomeric models were generated for both Gram-positive (*Rh.* AD45) and
231 Gram-negative *Variovorax* sp. WS11 (*V.* WS11) representatives (*Rh. opacus* PD630 was used in place
232 of *Rh.* AD45 for AldH1). For IsoA, additional dimeric models were generated using the AlphaFold2
233 “auto” model_type pipeline to evaluate conserved α_2 arrangements. A larger $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$ assembly was
234 subsequently modelled using AlphaFold2-Multimer v3 model_type, by combining multimer
235 predictions for IsoA + IsoB + 2×IsoE and 2×IsoA + 2×IsoB within PyMOL using the super alignment
236 command. This approach captured the canonical IsoMO core architecture (num_recycles = 1). The
237 final IsoMO core structure was reconstructed and verified with AlphaFold3 (Abramson et al., 2024).
238 Confidence scores (pLDDT, pTM, ipTM) for the modelled monomers/dimers and multimers were
239 generated using AlphaFold2 or AlphaFold3, respectively.

241 Structural visualisation, chain splitting, superposition, and residue highlighting were performed using
242 PyMOL v2.5 (Schrödinger and DeLano, 2020). IsoA models were additionally aligned to the
243 crystallographic structure of the soluble methane monooxygenase α -subunit MmoX (PDB ID: 1MTY;
244 Rosenzweig et al., 1993) after removal of non- α subunits. Iron-coordinating residues, conserved
245 motifs, and clade-specific loops were highlighted and labelled manually for clarity.

248 *Comparison of alpha-subunit sequences of different SDIMOs*

250 Protein sequences for the α -subunits of selected SDIMOs were compiled. IsoA sequences from the 11
251 isoprene degraders were included. A list of strains and accession numbers is provided in Table S5. The
252 dataset included six soluble methane monooxygenase (sMMO; MmoX) sequences from *Methylosinus*
253 *trichosporium* Ob3b, *Methylococcus capsulatus* (Bath), *Methylomonas methanica* MC09 (Boden et al.
254 2011; Zill et al. 2022), *Methylocella silvestris* BL2, *Methylocella tundrae* T4, and *Methylocella*
255 *palustris* BL2; butane monooxygenase (BmoX) from *Pseudomonas butanovora*; tetrahydrofuran
256 monooxygenase (ThmA) from *Pseudonocardia tetrahydrofuranoxydans*; propane monooxygenase
257 (PrmA) from *Gordonia* sp. TY5 and *Rh.* sp. RR1; propane monooxygenase (PmoC) from
258 *Mycobacterium* sp. M156; alkene monooxygenase (EtnC) from *Mycolicibacterium rhodesiae* JS60,
259 *Mycolicibacterium chubuense* NBB4, and *Nocardioides* sp. JS614; toluene ortho-monooxygenase

1 260 (TmoA3) from *Burkholderia cepacia* G4; toluene-4-monooxygenase (TmoA) from *Pseudomonas*
2 261 *mendocina* KR1; toluene-3-monooxygenase (TbuA) from *Ralstonia pickettii* PKO; and alkene
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4 262 monooxygenase (XamoA) from *Xanthobacter autotrophicus* Py2.

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7 264 Multiple sequence alignment and maximum-likelihood trees were performed as described previously.

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9 265 The alignment (Figure S16) has *Rh. AD45 IsoA* as the structural reference for secondary structure
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11 266 annotation and motif mapping. For the main SDIMO context tree (Figure 2), all IsoA sequences were
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13 267 retained along with one to two representative sequences per major SDIMO α -subunit clade (MmoX,
14 268 BmoX, PrmA, ThmA, TmoA) to highlight relationships without overloading the topology.

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19 271 *Residue-Level Comparison Between IsoA and MmoX*

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23 273 A focused alignment was constructed between the IsoA and MmoX sequences using MAFFT v7.505
24 274 (without trimming). Structural superpositions of IsoA monomers and dimers with MmoX (PDB:
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26 275 1MTY) were performed with PyMOL. Conserved secondary structural elements were inferred by
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28 276 aligning six representative MmoX sequences and visualized via ESPript, enabling cross-reference of α -
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30 277 helices, β -strands, and di-iron motifs between MmoX and IsoA (Figure 3; Figures S17 and S18).

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278 Results

280 Overview of *iso*-genes and genomic datasets

282 To investigate the diversity, conservation, and genomic context of the IsoMO and its associated
283 catabolic genes, we constructed a dataset of *iso* clusters from 11 confirmed bacterial genomes of *iso*-
284 type isoprene degraders from multiple taxonomic groups originating from diverse environments. These
285 included 8 Gram-positive strains, primarily from the genus *Rhodococcus*, along with representative
286 *Gordonia*, *Mycobacterium*, and *Nocardioides*, and the three Gram-negative isoprene degraders from
287 the family Comamonadaceae: *Ramlibacter* WS9, *Variovorax* WS11, and *Sphingopyxis* OPL5.

289 Although relatively few genomes are available, the dataset reflects broad taxonomic and ecological
290 diversity, with isolates recovered from estuarine, freshwater, soil and phyllosphere environments. Most
291 strains were obtained from enrichment experiments, using isoprene as the only source of carbon and
292 energy, often from leaves or soils associated with isoprene-emitting trees such as *Elaeis guineensis*,
293 *Populus alba*, and *Salix alba*. Following enrichment, bacteria isolates were purified and confirmed to
294 degrade isoprene through growth assays, along with detection of key *iso* genes (initially *isoA*). The
295 taxonomic affiliation, source of isolation, and relevant references for each strain are summarized in
296 Table 1, with detailed genome statistics provided in Table S1. Genome sizes ranged from 4.68 Mb to
297 12.7 Mb, and protein-coding genes varied from 4,400 to 10,800 per genome.

300 Organization and conservation of the *iso* gene cluster

302 Syntenic neighbourhood comparisons separate Gram-positive and Gram-negative taxa (Figure 1).
303 Homologous genes were identified by amino acid identity ($\geq 20\%$) and gene orientation was maintained
304 in the figure to reflect the native genomic organization and orientation of each gene. As expected, all
305 strains contained a conserved modular cluster of six genes encoding the IsoMO subunits (*isoA-F*),
306 typically followed by four glutathione-dependent genes (*isoG-J*). The aldehyde dehydrogenase gene
307 (*aldHI*), was located immediately downstream of *isoF* in most genomes, except for *Rh. AD45* in
308 which *aldHI* was absent from this locus (Dawson et al. 2020).

1 310 Two major patterns were apparent from the *iso* cluster visualization. Firstly, most *Rhodococcus*
2 311 genomes (except WS1, isolated at lower isoprene enrichment concentrations) showed a distinctive
3 312 modular organization characterized by duplications and rearrangements of the *isoGHIJ* module. This
4 313 suggests possible species-specific adaptation to environmental conditions or isoprene flux. Second,
5 314 Gram-positive and Gram-negative strains may be further distinguished by adjacent accessory genes. In
6 315 Gram-positives (*Rhodococcus*, *Nocardioides*, *Gordonia*, *Mycobacterium*), *gshA* was consistently
7 316 positioned upstream of *isoG*, *gshB* downstream of *isoF* also observed by Haarmann et al., 2025, and
8 317 *marR*-like regulator was usually present (absent only in *Mycobacterium*, which instead encoded MCE
9 318 family proteins and LysR-type regulator). In Gram-negatives (*Sphingopyxis*, *Ramlibacter*,
10 319 *Variovorax*), *gorA* (in charge of catalyzing glutathione disulfide to reduced glutathione; UniprotKB
11 320 P06715) was present upstream of *isoF*, and two of the genomes also carried a *lysR*-type regulator gene.
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23 323 **Pairwise amino acid sequence conservation of IsoMO and detoxification proteins**

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26 326 To further characterize the proteins encoded by the *iso* cluster, we calculated average amino acid
27 327 sequence lengths across the 11 selected genomes (Table S2). The IsoMO proteins were highly
28 328 consistent in length, with IsoA averaging 425 amino acids (± 1), IsoB 334 (± 2), IsoC 184 (± 1), IsoD
29 329 194 (± 3), IsoE 381 (± 2), and IsoF 326 (± 2). By contrast, glutathione-dependent detoxification protein
30 330 sizes were more variable, with IsoG averaging 177 amino acids (± 6), IsoH 206 (± 7), IsoI 219 (± 18),
31 331 and IsoJ 225 (± 18). The adjacent aldehyde dehydrogenase (AldH1), was highly consistent at 499
32 332 amino acids (± 0).
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40 333 Pairwise BLASTp comparisons were performed for each protein, with identity values grouped by
41 334 taxonomic comparison: Gram-positive vs. Gram-positive ($G^+ : G^+$), Gram-negative vs. Gram-negative
42 335 ($G^- : G^-$), and Gram-positive vs. Gram-negative ($G^+ : G^-$) (Table S3-S4). IsoA emerged as the most
43 336 conserved protein, with identities of 82.4–100 % ($G^+ : G^+$) and 81–100 % ($G^- : G^-$). Even across Gram
44 337 groups, conservation remained high (71.2–74.6 %), confirming its suitability as both a functional and
45 338 phylogenetic marker. In contrast, the IsoMO core β -subunit and reductase (IsoE and IsoF, respectively)
46 339 were among the least conserved, particularly in inter-group comparisons, with $G^+ : G^-$ identities of
47 340 47.3–54.1 % and 39.3–47.7 %, respectively. The detoxification enzymes IsoG, IsoH, IsoI, and IsoJ
48 341 also exhibited substantial divergence across Gram groups, with minimum inter-group identities ranging
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1 342 from 45.4 % to 58.2 %. AldH1 displayed intermediate conservation, with identities of 63.6–100 %
2 343 ($G^+ : G^+$) and 49.2–54.1 % ($G^+ : G^-$), consistent with a less central or more functionally flexible role.
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4 344

5 345 Overall, these comparisons show the center of the *iso* cluster (IsoA–C) is highly conserved across
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7 346 lineages, likely reflecting a strong purifying selection against detrimental mutations, contrasted by
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9 347 higher variability in the detoxification module. Nucleotide-level comparisons (Table S6) mirrored
10
11 348 these trends but showed greater variability, likely due to synonymous substitutions and divergence in
12 349 non-coding regions.
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14 350 15 16 351 17 352 **Phylogenetic analysis and alignment of proteins encoded by the *iso* cluster**

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21 354 To assess whether conservation patterns across the proteins encoded within the *iso* cluster reflect
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23 355 vertical inheritance, modular evolution, or recombination, we constructed maximum likelihood
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25 356 phylogenies based on amino acid sequences from proteins IsoA–F, AldH and IsoG–J from the selected
26 357 genomes (Figures S2A–S12A). In all cases, Gram-positive (G^+) and Gram-negative (G^-) amino acid
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28 358 sequences resolved as distinct, well-supported clades, consistent with long-term lineage-specific
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30 359 divergence, with pairwise amino acid identity values (described previously, Table S3) confirmed these
31 360 patterns, $G^+ : G^-$ comparisons consistently showing lower amino acid sequence identity than within-
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33 361 group comparisons.
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36 363 Protein analyses are summarized below, with phylogenetic trees (A), multiple sequence alignment (B),
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38 364 and AlphaFold models (C) shown in Figures S2–S12. The supplementary notes summarise the main
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40 365 phylogenetic and amino acid sequence alignment features for each protein, with G^+ / G^- variation
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42 366 profiles highlighted and conserved motifs referenced to *Rh*. AD45 numbering from ESPript.
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45 368 Structural models generated for each IsoMO protein from both *iso*-type model organisms (*Rh*.
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47 369 AD45, Gram-positive and *V*. WS11, Gram-negative) which consistently predicted well-conserved
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49 370 structural scaffolds across all components (Figures S2C–S12C). Structural overlays confirmed that the
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51 371 IsoMO multicomponent core, elements $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$ (that include key α -helical and β -sheet elements) are
52 372 retained across clades. Structural variation between clades was mostly found in loop insertions,
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54 373 termini, and surface-exposed segments, particularly in detoxification and electron transfer proteins.

55 374 These results provide a consistent picture: the proteins at the center of the IsoMO (encoded by genes in
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1 375 the center of the *iso* cluster: IsoA–C) are highly conserved across all clades and retain functional
2 376 motifs essential for di-iron catalysis and subunit assembly. Accessory proteins such as IsoG–J exhibit
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4 377 greater divergence and signs of duplication in Gram-positive taxa, while electron transfer components
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6 378 IsoD–F show intermediate variability, particularly in loop regions and termini. AldH1 appears loosely
7 379 linked, phylogenetically intermediate, and structurally conserved, possibly reflecting its more
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9 380 peripheral role in the catabolic pathway.

14 383 **Pairwise topological comparisons between *iso* gene trees**

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17 385 To quantify the degree of phylogenetic congruence among the *iso* genes, we computed pairwise
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19 386 distances between gene trees using four metrics: normalized Robinson–Foulds (RF), weighted RF,
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21 387 normalized subtree prune-and-regraft (SPR), and branch score distance. These metrics capture both
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23 388 topological similarity and evolutionary rate variation. We focus on amino acid–based trees (Figure
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25 389 S13), as the nucleotide trees yielded comparable results but with greater uncertainty (Figure S14).

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28 391 Heatmaps showed the IsoMO core structural genes *isoA*, *isoB* and *isoE*, exhibited a high congruence
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30 392 across all metrics, forming a tightly coherent cluster in both RF and SPR analyses (Figures S13 and
31 393 S15; de Oliveira Martins et al., 2016). The same can be observed between the reductase component
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33 394 *isoF* gene and the structural gene *isoE*. In contrast, detoxification genes *isoG*, *isoH*, *isoI*, and *isoJ*
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35 395 showed higher pairwise distances, particularly in normalized RF and SPR metrics, consistent with their
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37 396 history of duplication, diversification, and modular evolution. They tend to cluster together on an MDS
38 397 map, however, probably due to similar (alternative) evolutionary trajectories (Figure S15). *aldH1* and
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40 398 particularly *isoE* consistently showed partial congruence with the IsoMO genes, supporting *aldH1*'s
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42 399 intermediate evolutionary linkage.

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45 401 Histogram distributions of RF distances (Figure S14) show how both amino acid and nucleotide
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47 402 alignment yield broadly similar tree-to-tree distance patterns across all metrics. Overall values were
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49 403 higher for nucleotide- than for amino acid–based trees, indicating slightly more diverse nucleotide-
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51 404 based phylogenies. In all cases, most comparisons fall at intermediate distance values, with only a
52 405 small number of very similar tree pairs.

1 407 These tree-based comparisons reinforce the modular organization of the *iso* cluster. The comparatively
2 408 low diversity of the monooxygenase components supports the hypothesis that the IsoMO core and the
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4 409 detoxification module follow separate evolutionary trajectories. The intermediate positioning of *isoD*-
5 410 *F* and *aldH1* supports a mixed evolutionary trajectory, with components shaped by both functional
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7 411 linkage and independent adaptation.
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12 414 **IsoA and its phylogenetic position with reference to α -subunits of other SDIMOs**

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16 416 To place IsoA within the broader context of SDIMO diversity, we constructed a maximum-likelihood
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18 417 phylogeny using representative α -subunits from well-characterized SDIMO families, including
19 418 methane, alkene, toluene, and propane monooxygenases. IsoA sequences from all 11 isoprene-
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21 419 degrading genomes formed a monophyletic clade, distinct from other SDIMO lineages (Figure 2;
22
23 420 Supplementary Figures 16). Within the IsoA clade, Gram-positive and Gram-negative sequences
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25 421 segregated into sister subgroups with strong bootstrap support, reflecting vertical inheritance shaped by
26 422 host taxonomy. MmoX, the α -subunit of soluble methane monooxygenase (sMMO), formed a separate
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28 423 lineage within the tree, underscoring the evolutionary divergence between methane- and isoprene-
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30 424 oxidizing systems. This topology supports a single IsoA lineage specialized for isoprene oxidation and
31 425 structured primarily by host phylogeny, consistent with vertical inheritance within Gram groups and
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33 426 substrate-specialized lineage separation within the SDIMO superfamily.
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38 429 **Structural comparison of IsoA and MmoX reveals conservation of important residues**

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42 431 To investigate structural conservation between isoprene and methane monooxygenases, we aligned
43 432 IsoA models with the crystal structure of MmoX from *Methylococcus capsulatus* Bath (PDB: 1MTY;
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45 433 Rosenzweig et al., 1997). Multiple sequence alignment revealed that all six residues responsible for di-
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47 434 iron coordination in MmoX (e.g., E114, H147, E243) were conserved in IsoA (e.g., E110, H143,
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49 435 E237), suggesting preservation of the catalytic core architecture (Figure 3; Table 2; Figures S17–S18).
50 436 The functional roles of these residues in IsoMO are putative and inferred from structural homology
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52 437 rather than experimental verification; no site-directed mutagenesis or biochemical data currently
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54 438 confirm their activity. Nevertheless, the strong structural and sequence correspondence provides a
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1 439 compelling *in silico* framework to guide future mutagenesis and mechanistic studies of isoprene
2 440 oxidation.
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4 441
5 442 Protein structural overlays of IsoA (*Rh.* AD45) and MmoX showed high similarity in their α -helical
6 443 cores and active-site configuration (Figure 4A–C). Differences were observed in loop regions near the
7 444 substrate-binding site and at the N-/C-termini, including substitutions in residues predicted to be in line
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9 445 with channel for entry of substrates and exit of products (e.g., Q234 in IsoA vs. E240 in MmoX),
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11 446 which may contribute to isoprene specificity. Protein structure models of IsoA achieved high overall
12 447 confidence (mean pLDDT \approx 91.8), with the α -helical core and di-iron ligating motifs resolved at very
13
14 448 high confidence (>95). Lower scores (<70) were confined to terminal extensions and surface-exposed
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16 449 loops, consistent with their structural variability. Predicted alignment error (PAE) values were
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18 450 uniformly low within the catalytic core, supporting the reliability of the structural comparison with
19 451 MmoX. Together, these features indicate that IsoA retains the hallmark SDIMO fold and di-iron
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21 452 catalytic geometry while exhibiting clade-specific divergence in substrate-binding regions.
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28 455 **IsoA dimer modeling and clade-specific conservation**

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31 457 Multimer predictions for IsoA from *Rh.* AD45 and *V.* WS11 yielded stable dimeric assemblies with
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33 458 symmetric head-to-tail arrangements. The predicted interface was dominated by conserved α -helical
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35 459 contacts, and the overall fold was highly consistent across both clades (Figure S19). Structural
36
37 460 superposition of the two dimer models showed near-complete alignment of core helices and di-iron-
38 461 binding residues, with minor differences restricted to loop extensions and termini. Model confidence
39
40 462 was high, with the *Rh.* AD45 IsoA dimer achieving a mean pLDDT of 90.8 (median 95.4), with over
41
42 463 80% of residues scoring above 90. Predicted template modeling scores (pTM = 0.86) and interface
43 464 scores (ipTM = 0.83) supported a reliable dimer arrangement. Predicted alignment error (PAE) values
44
45 465 were low within monomers (mean ~ 6 Å) and moderate at the interface (median ~ 8.3 Å), consistent
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47 466 with confident core contacts and some flexibility in loop regions. Together, these results suggest that
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49 467 IsoA dimerization is a structurally conserved feature of IsoMO systems and likely critical for
50 468 maintaining the catalytic configuration across diverse isoprene degraders.
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55 471 **Structural modelling of the IsoMO putative catalytic core**

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1
2 473 AlphaFold3 multimer predictions for the IsoMO from *Rh. AD45* recovered the expected $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$ IsoMO
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4 474 core assembly comprising two IsoA (α ; cyan), two IsoE (β ; purple), and two IsoB (γ ; green) subunits
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6 475 (Figure 5). Conserved α -helical bundles within IsoA form the di-iron active site, while the β - and γ -
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8 476 subunits provide peripheral stabilising contacts consistent with the SDIMO. The IsoMO core was
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10 477 modelled with high global and interface confidence (pTM = 0.88; ipTM = 0.86 for *Rh. AD45*),
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12 478 indicating a reliable subunit orientation and well-defined assembly interface (Abramson et al., 2024,
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14 479 Jumper et al., 2021). Residue-level confidence was also high for conserved regions (pLDDT > 90),
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16 480 confirming a robustly folded catalytic scaffold. Lower scores (<50) were limited to short terminal or
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18 481 surface-exposed regions, consistent with expected flexibility in non-core segments.

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21 483 Structural superposition of the IsoMO core with the sMMO hydroxylase from *Methylococcus*
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23 484 *capsulatus* Bath (PDB: 1MTY) revealed strong overall correspondence specifically between the $\alpha_2\beta_2$
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25 485 architectures, including alignment of conserved α -helical bundles and di-iron centres (Figure S20, refer
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27 486 to IsoA residues in Figure 4). Together, these results provide a high-confidence structural framework
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488 **Discussion**

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6 490 This study used isolate-based genomic and structural comparison analyses to investigate the evolution
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8 491 and function of IsoMO across diverse bacterial taxa. By addressing key questions in microbial ecology
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10 492 (Antwis et al., 2017), we provide insights into microbial evolutionary processes and functional
11 493 diversity underlying isoprene degradation. Protein phylogenetic and comparative genomic analysis
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13 494 support strong conservation of the IsoMO catalytic core alongside lineage-specific variation in
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15 495 accessory and detoxification genes. Together, these patterns support the view that IsoMO is maintained
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17 496 as a vertically inherited, functionally constrained enzymatic module, with surrounding regulatory and
18 497 redox components exhibiting greater evolutionary flexibility, potentially in response to host-specific
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20 498 ecological and physiological pressures.

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23 499 Structural modelling reinforces this interpretation. Despite sequence divergence between Gram-
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25 500 positive and Gram-negative taxa, the IsoMO core retains a conserved multicomponent architecture
26 501 characteristic of Group1 soluble di-iron monooxygenases. IsoA carries a highly conserved di-iron
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28 502 center closely resembling MmoX (Rosenzweig et al. 1997). This structural continuity supports the
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30 503 view that sMMO and IsoMO arose either from a shared ancestral monooxygenase, as suggested by
31 504 Leahy (2003), or evolutionary convergence, with both enzymes subsequently adapting to distinct
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33 505 carbon substrates. IsoA was consistently the most conserved subunit, supporting its role as the
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35 506 evolutionary anchor of the *iso* cluster and the principal determinant of isoprene oxidation (Carrion et
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37 507 al., 2018, Crombie et al., 2015). Substrate-channel differences relative to MmoX (e.g., G208, C151,
38 508 M184, E240 versus V202, D147, V178, Q234) may underpin isoprene specificity (Merkx et al., 2001;
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40 509 Borodina et al., 2007) and provide a framework for targeted mutagenesis and mechanistic studies.

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43 510 From an ecological perspective, this modular organization may facilitate its persistence across diverse
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45 511 environments and host taxa. Isoprene-degrading and methane-oxidising bacteria have been reported in
46 512 plant-associated habitats such as the phyllosphere of *Sphagnum* moss (e.g. *Methylocella* spp., Dedysch
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48 513 et al. 2005; Crombie et al., 2025). Because *Sphagnum* hosts active degraders of both methane and
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50 514 isoprene, it represents a natural environment in which the evolutionary history of these
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52 515 monooxygenases may converge at the interphase between aerial and submerged tissue, supporting the
53 516 analysis and comparison of IsoA to MmoX and for exploring how related monooxygenases contribute
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55 517 to carbon cycling.

1 518 Within this ecological context, genomic and functional patterns may also help explain observations
2 519 from microcosm studies. In *Sphagnum* moss, isoprene degradation was inhibited by 1-octyne but not
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4 520 by acetylene (Crombie et al., 2025; Dawson et al., 2020), consistent with a target within the conserved
5 521 IsoMO active site. Structural models therefore provide a framework for interpreting such inhibition
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7 522 and for developing future imaging or probe-based approaches to study IsoMO activity *in situ*. Future
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9 523 studies should examine how substrates and inhibitors interact with IsoMO at the structural and
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11 524 molecular level, how variation in these interactions influences the microbial community adaptation and
12 525 plant–microbiome interactions under environmental change.
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15 526 Beyond these ecological implications, our phylogenetic analyses also help clarify long-standing
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17 527 misannotation issues, which likely arise from the limited representation of verified *iso* cluster
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19 528 sequences in public databases (Dawson et al., 2023). Moving forward, a combined strategy that
20 529 couples direct phenotypic assays with indirect, sequence-based inference of active *iso*-type degraders
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22 530 (Larke-Mejía et al., 2019; Ledford et al., 2025) will be essential for improving database accuracy and
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24 531 strengthening ecological and evolutionary analyses. IsoA grouped closely with TmoA- and XamoA-
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26 532 like α -subunits (Dawson et al., 2020), indicating that further comparative work on these related
27 533 SDIMOs will be essential for identifying residues that differentiate substrate selection across isoprene-,
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29 534 toluene-, and alkene-oxidizing enzymes.
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32 535 Overall, these structural and genomic insights highlight that IsoMO represents a conserved and stable
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34 536 microbial function with direct ecological significance. Because isoprene degradation is the only known
35 537 biological sink of one of the most abundantly produced biogenic volatile organic compounds,
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37 538 understanding the evolutionary stability and mechanistic basis of IsoMO may be critical for predicting
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39 539 how microbial communities influence isoprene fluxes, plant–microbe interactions and VOC-driven
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41 540 ecosystem processes.
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45 542 **Conclusions**

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48 544 This study presents an integrated evolutionary and structural analysis of isoprene monooxygenase
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50 545 (IsoMO) from confirmed isoprene-degrading isolates. We demonstrate that IsoMO comprises a highly
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52 546 conserved $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$ di-iron monooxygenase core, closely related to the soluble methane monooxygenase
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54 547 hydroxylase, embedded within a more flexible accessory framework. This organisation supports a
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56 548 model in which the *iso* gene cluster combines vertical inheritance of a functionally constrained
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1 549 catalytic unit with adaptive diversification of auxiliary components. By establishing a deep structural
2 550 and evolutionary relationship between IsoMO and other soluble di-iron monooxygenases, this work
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4 551 reveals that the enzymatic machinery responsible for oxidising two of Earth's most abundant biogenic
5 552 volatile organic compounds (methane and isoprene) shares a conserved catalytic framework that has
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7 553 diversified to support contrasting ecological roles. The strong conservation of IsoA further supports its
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9 554 use as a reliable molecular marker for isoprene degradation and for identifying active isoprene-
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11 555 degrading populations in environmental studied. Future work should prioritize isolation and
12 556 experimental validation of predicted IsoMO complexes and structure-guided inhibitor interactions.
13
14 557 Integrating structural insights with inhibitor-based imaging, microcosm, and mesocosm studies will
15
16 558 improve understandind of microbial communities influence VOC fluxes under changing environmental
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18 559 conditions.

22 562 **Funding**

24 563
26 564 This work was supported by the European Union through a Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions
27
28 565 Independent Fellowship [grant number 101150622— u-Arctic] to **N.L.L.M.** and European Research
29
30 566 Council Advanced Grant [grant number 694578—IsoMet] to **J.C.M. L.d.O.M.** was supported by the
31 567 UK Office for Life Sciences (OLS) through funding provided to the North West sub-national Secure
32
33 568 Data Environment (NW SDE) and to the Cheshire and Merseyside Integrated Care Board (CM ICB).
34
35 569 Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the
36
37 570 European Union or the Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting
38 571 authority can be held responsible for them.
39

43 574 **Acknowledgements**

45 575
47 576 This project was supported by The Danish National Research Foundation within the Center for
48
49 577 Volatile Interactions (VOLT, DNRF168). We would also like to acknowledge Laura Martinez Alvarez
50 578 and Mario Rodriguez Mestre (University of Copenhagen) for insights into structural models with
51
52 579 AlphaFold. Artificial intelligence (AI) was used to interpret some of the AlphaFold outputs ~~correct the~~
53
54 580 ~~bibliography~~ and improve the clarity of the discussion in the second rebuttal.
55
56 581

582

Authors contributions

584

585 **Nasmille L. Larke-Mejía:** Conceptualization (equal), Methodology (lead), Formal analysis (lead),
586 Writing – original draft preparation (lead), Writing-Review and Editing (lead), Funding acquisition
587 (equal). **J. Colin Murrell:** Conceptualization (equal), Writing-Review and Editing (equal), Funding
588 acquisition (equal). **Leonardo de Oliveira Martins:** Formal analysis (phylogenetic congruence),
589 Writing-Review and Editing (limited contribution).

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Data availability

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594 The data underlying this article are available in ERDA at <https://sid.erda.dk/sharelink/CY7eSNcgUJ>.

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Gene-by-gene phylogenetic analysis and alignment of proteins sequence alignment of encoded by the iso cluster

Gene-by-gene Protein analyses are summarized below, with phylogenetic trees (A), multiple sequence alignment (B), and AlphaFold models (C) shown in Figures S2–S12. Below we summarise the main phylogenetic and sequence alignment features for each **protein gene**, with G^+/G^- variation profiles highlighted and conserved motifs referenced to *Rh.* AD45 numbering from the multiple sequence alignment.

IsoA (α -subunit of the IsoMO; average length 504 amino acids, Figure S2; $n=11$) was the most conserved **protein gene** within the *iso* cluster, with pairwise amino acid identities of 82–100% among Gram-positive sequences, 81–100% among Gram-negative sequences, and 71–75% between Gram groups. Maximum likelihood phylogenies (Fig. S2A, 507 aligned positions) consistently resolved Gram-positive and Gram-negative IsoA sequences as distinct, well-supported clades. Indicating long-term lineage-specific divergence while having the lowest phylogenetic diversity (sum of branch lengths on the tree = 1.47). Multiple sequence alignment (Fig. S2B, full annotation Figure 3 and Table 2) revealed conservation of hallmark SDIMO motifs based on Leahy *et al.*, 2003 [and Jones *et al.*, 2020](#). Structural predictions of IsoA (Fig. S2C) confirmed the high conservation of the α -subunit fold between Gram-positive (*Rh.* AD45) and Gram-negative (*V.* WS11) representatives, with both monomeric and dimeric models showing nearly identical core helices. Superposition highlighted subtle clade-specific loop variations, while the di-iron cluster ligating residues remained invariant. AlphaFold2 models yielded high-confidence predictions (average pLDDT ~ 91.8), with particularly strong confidence at regions likely to be involved in di-iron binding motifs and catalytic helices (highlighted in pink/red ribbon representation in the monomer for clarity). Together, these features underscore the strong purifying selection acting on the IsoMO catalytic core, conserved sequence of the catalytic center of the cluster and reinforce IsoA as a robust phylogenetic and functional marker.

IsoB (γ -subunit of the IsoMO; average length 92 amino acids, Figure S3; $n=11$) formed two strongly supported clades in phylogenetic trees (Fig. S3A, 89 aligned positions), clearly separating Gram-positive and Gram-negative representatives. *Rhodococcus* sequences formed a

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3 compact Gram-positive subcluster (bootstrap support >99%), while Gram-negative taxa showed
4 longer branches, indicating greater divergence. Pairwise sequence identity was high within
5 groups ($G^+ : G^+$ 85–100%; $G^- : G^-$ 81–97%), but dropped across groups ($G^+ : G^-$ <75%), consistent
6 with taxonomic divergence across the *iso* cluster. The tree shows the second largest phylogenetic
7 diversity (sum of branches = 4.2). Multiple sequence alignment (Fig. S3B) showed the
8 conservation of residues 13–44 (*Rh.* AD45 numbering). Models for *Rh.* AD45 and *V.* WS11 (Fig.
9 S3C) showed strong overlap in the central β/α framework. Confidence scores showed very high
10 pLDDT values (>90) across the core $\beta 1-\alpha 2$ region and moderate scores (70–85) in the variable
11 loops, supporting confident prediction of conserved structural features while acknowledging
12 flexibility in less-conserved regions.
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22 **IsoC** (the Rieske-type ferredoxin; average length 111 amino acids, Figure S4; n=11) was among
23 the most conserved components of the IsoMO complex, with pairwise identities ranging from
24 88–100% within Gram-positive strains and 85–100% within Gram-negatives. Phylogenetic
25 analysis (Fig. S4A, 112 aligned positions) recovered strongly supported separation into Gram-
26 positive and Gram-negative clades, with short internal branches indicative of limited divergence
27 and recent common ancestry. Multiple sequence alignment (Fig. S4B) revealed complete
28 conservation of several hallmark Rieske motifs across all taxa, including the CPHQ segment
29 (C49–Q52) and the TCRAH motif (T67–H71) which coordinate the [2Fe-2S] cluster (Davidson
30 *et al.*, 1992; Colbert *et al.*, 2000). Structural predictions (Fig. S4C) confirmed the near-identical
31 fold of IsoC in both *Rh.* AD45 and *V.* WS11, with conserved packing of the β -sheet core and
32 outward-facing α -helices. All conserved residues fell within high-confidence regions (pLDDT
33 >95) in AlphaFold2 models, supporting their structural and functional significance.
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44 **IsoD** (the coupling subunit; average length 110 amino acids, Figure S5, n = 11) exhibited high
45 conservation across taxa, forming distinct Gram-positive and Gram-negative clades in the
46 phylogenetic tree (Fig. S5A, 104 aligned positions). Within the *Rhodococcus* clade, sequences
47 were nearly identical, reflected by short branch lengths. Multiple sequence alignment (Fig. S5B)
48 showed strict conservation of a glutamate-rich segment (E72–E81, *Rh.* AD45 numbering) and
49 adjacent β -strand/ α -helix elements that may contribute to docking interactions with the
50 monooxygenase as seen in the phenol hydroxylase and regulatory protein complex for
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3 *Pseudomonas* sp. OX1 (Sazinsky *et al.*, 2007). Beyond this conserved block, variation was
4 largely confined to surface-exposed loops. AlphaFold2 structural predictions (Fig. S5C)
5 confirmed that IsoD adopts a consistent β -sheet/ α -helix scaffold across both Gram-positive and
6 Gram-negative representatives, with the glutamate-rich region and surrounding secondary
7 structure predicted with high confidence (pLDDT > 92). These features support the role of IsoD
8 as a structurally stable, evolutionarily constrained coupling protein that mediates electron
9 transfer complex assembly rather than acting as a redox-active subunit itself.
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17 **IsoE** (β -subunit of the IsoMO; average length 348 amino acids, Figure S6, n = 11) exhibited a
18 deep G^+/G^- split, with intra-clade identities of 80–100%, but $G^+:G^-$ values dropping to 47–54%.
19 Phylogenetic trees resolved *Rhodococcus* sequences as a tight G^+ subcluster with short internal
20 branch lengths, whereas G^- sequences displayed longer branches, consistent with higher
21 divergence (Fig. S6A, 339 aligned positions). Multiple sequence alignment (Fig. S6B)
22 highlighted a conserved β -strand-rich region (residues 148–180, *Rh.* AD45 numbering) and a
23 short glycine-rich segment near positions ~45–55 that is conserved (Walters *et al.*, 1999).
24 Structural predictions (Fig. S6C) showed a highly conserved β -subunit scaffold with near-
25 identical core β -sheet/ α -helix architecture across *Rh.* AD45 and *V.* WS11; clade-specific
26 differences were confined to surface-exposed loops. Per-residue model confidence was highest in
27 the core scaffold (pLDDT >95), underscoring structural conservation of the β -subunit.
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38 **IsoF** (the reductase; average length 343 amino acids, Figure S7, n = 11) was the least conserved
39 of the electron transfer components, with inter-group amino acid identities of 39–48%. This was
40 confirmed by the largest phylogenetic diversity based on its phylogeny (sum of branches = 6.24).
41 Phylogenetic analyses (Fig. S7A, 332 aligned positions) resolved deep Gram-positive and Gram-
42 negative clades, with long internal branches observed particularly among G^- sequences. Despite
43 this divergence, the core β -sheet/ α -helix scaffold was preserved across all taxa. Multiple
44 sequence alignment (Fig. S7B) revealed strict conservation of motifs within IsoF sequences,
45 including a conserved YECASG segment (residues 35–40, *Rh.* AD45 numbering), a CGxC motif
46 (42–45), and the WAD motif (58–60), all of which were invariant across sequences and may be
47 critical for maintaining structural integrity and mediating redox interactions (e.g., Sevrioukova *et*
48 *al.*, 2004). Sequence divergence was concentrated in loop regions and the C-terminal tail, where
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3 Gram-negative taxa exhibited clade-specific length variation and compositional changes.
4 Structural predictions (Fig. S7C) confirmed that these variable segments correspond to solvent-
5 exposed regions, leaving the conserved core intact. AlphaFold2 models for *Rh. AD45* and *V.*
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7 WS11 IsoF showed high pLDDT scores (>80) in the conserved scaffold and reduced confidence
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9 in peripheral loops, supporting the structural stability of the core and flexibility of accessory
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11 regions.
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15 **IsoG** (putative CoA-transferase, average length 381 amino acids, Fig. S8, n = 10 full-length
16 sequences in this dataset) resolved into well-supported Gram-positive and Gram-negative clades,
17 with *Rhodococcus* sequences clustering tightly within the Gram-positive group (Fig. S8A, 398
18 aligned positions). Consistent with pairwise identities ($G^+ : G^-$ 49.4–60.7%), the Gram split was
19 accompanied by longer internal branches among Gram-negative sequences. Multiple sequence
20 alignment (Fig. S8B) revealed several conserved features characteristic of CoA-transferases.
21 These include the candidate glutamate residues at positions E33 and E392, or D165 from the
22 enzyme family, as conserved in all sequences, that may be involved in the CoA transfer of Frc
23 CoA transferases (Hackmann, 2022; *Rix et al.*, 2023). Additionally, the GxG-like motifs at G36,
24 G101 and G121 were identified. These motifs were conserved across clades, while lineage-
25 specific indels and substitutions occurred primarily in peripheral loops. AlphaFold
26 superpositions of IsoG from *Rh. AD45* and *V. WS11* predicted nearly identical α/β -domain folds
27 and conserved active-site geometry, with structural variation largely confined to solvent-exposed
28 surface loops (Fig. S8C). Conserved active-site residues were modeled with high confidence
29 (pLDDT >95), supporting IsoG's functional annotation as a CoA-transferase in the isoprene
30 degradation pathway.
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45 **IsoH** (NAD⁺-dependent dehydrogenase subunit; average length 226 amino acids, Figure S9,
46 n = 11) resolved into clearly separated Gram-positive and Gram-negative clades, with evidence
47 of recent duplication in Gram-positive taxa. *Rhodococcus* sequences formed a tight Gram-
48 positive subcluster with short internal branches and strong bootstrap support, whereas Gram-
49 negative sequences showed greater divergence (Fig. S9A). Despite this variation, multiple
50 sequence alignment (Fig. S9B) and structural predictions using AlphaFold2 (Fig. S9C) showed
51 nearly identical β -sheet/ α -helix cores in *Rh. AD45* and *V. WS11* IsoH, with differences confined
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3 to solvent-exposed loops. Model confidence was high (mean pLDDT ~91 for AD45 and ~89 for
4 WS11), supporting a conserved fold and cofactor-binding architecture despite clade-specific
5 sequence divergence.
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10 **IsoI** (glutathione S-transferase-like subunit, average length 238 amino acids, Figure S10;
11 n = 11), formed strongly supported Gram-positive and Gram-negative clades (Fig. S10A).
12 Pairwise identities were lower between clades (45–53%) than within clades, consistent with
13 functional divergence. Multiple sequence alignment (Fig. S10B) revealed several highly
14 conserved glycine- and polar-rich segments, including a canonical GXG loop (G157–G159, *Rh.*
15 AD45 numbering) implicated in glutathione binding, as well as conserved core β -strands and α -
16 helices typical of GST enzymes (Wilce *et al.*, 1994). Clade-specific divergence was concentrated
17 in surface-exposed loops, particularly among Gram-negative sequences, where lineage-specific
18 insertions and polarity shifts were observed. AlphaFold2 structural models (Fig. S10C)
19 confirmed preservation of the canonical GST α/β scaffold in both *Rh.* AD45 and *V.* WS11, with
20 high per-residue confidence (pLDDT >90 across ~92% of residues). These results support
21 classification of IsoI as a structurally conserved GST-like enzyme with peripheral adaptations
22 across clades.
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34 **IsoJ** (glutathione S-transferase-like subunit, average length 238 amino acids, Figure S11;
35 n = 11), phylogenetic trees resolved *Rhodococcus* sequences as a tight Gram-positive subcluster,
36 and despite the rooting artefact imposed by the midpoint rooting on highly diverged G-
37 compared to G+, Gram-positive and Gram-negative do form monophyletic clusters. (Fig. S11A,
38 237 aligned positions). Multiple sequence alignment (Fig. S11B) and AlphaFold2 models of *Rh.*
39 AD45 and *V.* WS11 (Fig. S11C) confirmed preservation of the canonical GST β/α scaffold, with
40 minor clade-specific deviations restricted to solvent-exposed loops. Structural confidence was
41 high (mean pLDDT ~91 for AD45 and ~90 for WS11), supporting robust core structural
42 conservation.
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51 **AldH1** (aldehyde dehydrogenase, average length 465 amino acids, Figure S12; n = 10), resolved
52 into compact G⁺ and G⁻ clades with intermediate inter-group conservation (49–54%).
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Phylogenetic topologies broadly mirrored organismal relationships, with Gram-positive

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3 sequences clustering tightly and Gram-negative taxa forming a distinct sister group (Fig. S12A,
4 474 aligned positions). Multiple sequence alignment (Fig. S12B) and structural overlays of
5 AlphaFold2 models (Fig. S12C) confirmed conservation of the catalytic core of this protein
6 across Gram-positive and Gram-negative homologues, with loop-level variation confined to
7 solvent-exposed regions (Ahvazi *et al.*, 2000). Model confidence was uniformly high (mean
8 pLDDT >90 for core β/α elements, 70–85 in loops), supporting the assignment of AldH1 as a
9 catalytically competent NAD^+ -dependent aldehyde dehydrogenase that plays a more auxiliary
10 role relative to the IsoMO core components.
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21 When looking at the MDS plot (Fig. S15): left panels are topology only, right panels account for
22 branch lengths. IsoA and IsoB are topologically very similar (confirmed by looking at individual
23 trees, only *Nocardioides* location changes). And both are not far from IsoF when branches are
24 considered (same quadrant in panels at the right): despite the topology being more different.
25 Another grouping appears between IsoH, IsoI, and IsoG topologically. And this is joined by isoC
26 and AldH1 looking at branch lengths. That is, even though the topologies (branching patterns)
27 are different, the branch lengths are relatively similar.
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36 The heatmap (Fig. S13) is less visual than the phylogenies, but allows to see actual pairwise gene
37 distances (in terms of their evolutionary history). For instance, we see that IsoA and IsoB tend to
38 be close to each other irrespective of distance. Same thing between IsoE and IsoF, but not
39 between IsoC and IsoD. IsoE and AldH1 tend to be close to all other trees (their rows or columns
40 are closer to light blue than to brown).
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Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table S1. Isoprene-degrading bacterial strains isolated and with sequenced genomes.

Isolate	RefSeq	Scaffolds (contigs)	N50	L50	Total length (Mb)	Protein count	GC%	Genome neighbour (symmetrical identity; gapped)*
<i>Rhodococcus AD45</i>	GCA_000949305.1	9	1,521,985	2	6.79479	6029	61.7	
<i>Rhodococcus opacus PD630</i>	GCA_000599545.1	10	8,376,953	1	9.16903	8942	67.2	
<i>Rhodococcus LB1</i>	GCA_001583455.1	448 (526)	48,257	62	10.752	9270	66.6	<i>Rhodococcus</i> SC4 (82%)
<i>Rhodococcus SC4</i>	GCA_001555475.1	345 (419)	71,344	41	10.5719	9123	66.7	<i>Rhodococcus</i> LB1 (82%)
<i>Rhodococcus ACPA1</i>	GCA_002300195.1	47 (48)	1,120,468	4	10.0608	8808	66.9	<i>Rhodococcus</i> LB1 (81.56%)
<i>Rhodococcus ACPA4</i>	GCA_002300185.1	9 (11)	3,616,808	1	7.06712	6247	61.1	metagenome <i>Rhodococcus</i> sp. PMG_254 (98.78%)
<i>Rhodococcus ACSI</i>	GCA_002300155.1	40 (41)	676,616	5	10.8914	9508	67	<i>Rhodococcus</i> ACPA1 (64.49%)
<i>Rhodococcus WS1</i>	GCA_003797745.1	8	2,655,236	2	6.56024	5943	62.3	<i>Rhodococcus</i> WS7 (99%)
<i>Rhodococcus WS3</i>	GCA_003797085.1	19 (21)	1,535,683	2	6.85616	6095	61.7	metagenome <i>Rhodococcus</i> sp. PMG_254 (98.82%)
<i>Rhodococcus WS4</i>	GCA_006543605.1	1221	40,486	91	12.7295	10854	66.4	<i>Rhodococcus</i> ACPA1 (56.96%)
<i>Rhodococcus WS7</i>	GCA_006543615.1	180	453,949	5	6.6282	6053	62.4	<i>Rhodococcus</i> WS1 (99.34%)
<i>Gordonia i37</i>	GCA_002043085.1	721	16524	122	6.22816	5486	66.8	<i>Gordonia</i> sp. NB4-1Y (84.00%; 97.44%)
<i>Gordonia OPL2</i>	GCA_003797825.1	146	149,633	11	5.7959	5169	67.3	
<i>Mycobacterium AT1</i>	GCA_002043095.1	129 (143)	105263	22	7.07238	6620	67.2	<i>Mycobacterium</i> sp. Root135 (73.85%)
<i>Nocardioides WS12</i>	GCA_014108865.1	1	5,171,066	1	5.17107	4925	68.7	<i>Nocardioides</i> sp. Root682 (64.35%; 88.15%)
<i>Ramlibacter WS9</i>	GCA_003797765.1	180	224764	10	6.98085	6517	65.4	
<i>Variovorax WS11</i>	GCA_010499245.1	5	1304680	2	8.48961	7789	67.3901	<i>Variovorax</i> sp CF079 (54.52%; 87.31%) <i>Variovorax</i> RA8 (51.8%; 90.121%)
<i>Sphingopyxis OPL5</i>	GCA_003797775.2	1	4,676,975	1	4.67697	4418	65.9	

*The listed bacterial name corresponds to the closest genome neighbour identified in the alignment-based comparison. The percentages indicate the symmetrical identity between the two genomes, calculated for the whole genome and with gaps included.

Supplementary Table S2. Protein lengths of isoprene metabolic cluster genes (IsoA–F, IsoG–J, and AldH1) across 11 selected isoprene-degrading bacterial genomes.

Genus	strain	IsoG	IsoH	IsoI	IsoJ	AldH	IsoA	IsoB	IsoC	IsoD	IsoE	IsoF
<i>Rhodococcus</i>	AD45	401	226	238	233	-*	514	94	114	110	342	345
<i>Rhodococcus</i>	PD630	405	226	238	233	451	507	94	114	110	340	345
<i>Rhodococcus</i>	LB1	173	226	238	233	451	507	94	114	110	340	345
<i>Rhodococcus</i>	WS7	401	226	238	233	451	507	94	114	110	340	345
<i>Mycobacterium</i>	AT1	401	226	238	234	450	511	94	114	108	342	331
<i>Gordonia</i>	i37	402	226	239	236	477	506	95	121	106	338	341
<i>Gordonia</i>	OPL2	401	226	239	236	478	496	95	109	106	340	342
<i>Nocardioides</i>	WS12	395	226	237	250	477	498	89	118	110	340	355
<i>Ramlibacter</i>	WS9	402	226	238	239	465	497	88	97	104	343	342
<i>Sphingopyxis</i>	OPL5	405	226	225	243	466	497	87	112	106	367	329
<i>Variovorax</i>	WS11	402	227	238	242	475	500	88	111	97	367	344

Supplementary Table S3. Pairwise amino acid identity percentages for each protein in the isoprene metabolic gene cluster (IsoA–F, IsoG–J, and AldH) across 11 isoprene-degrading strains. Values were derived from BLASTp comparisons.

		100-90							89-80		79-70		69-60		59-50		49-35		34-0						
IsoA		AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5	IsoG	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5	
	AD45	100												AD45	100										
	PD630	91.12	100											PD630	90.52	100									
	LB1	91.32	99.41	100										LB1	83.32	80.435	100								
	WS7	90.73	93.549	93.989	100									WS7	90.02	95.876	78.61	100							
	AT1	83.217	88.219	85.52	85.52	100								AT1	84.329	87.878	76.3	86.53	100						
	i37	85.657	90.657	88.8	89.02	85.94	100							i37	78.986	82.659	70.83	83.54	81.34	100					
	OPL2	86.769	90.04	89.72	89.327	86.329	92.54	100						OPL2	77.53	80.81	68.326	80.81	80.03	89.8	100				
	WS12	83.987	87.93	87.93	86.12	82.441	84.71	84.74	100					WS12	75.326	76.71	68.326	76.95	74.549	74.81	73.986	100			
	WS9	71.23	73.72	73.72	72.769	73.31	74.659	72.32	72.98	100				WS9	60.71	60.435	57.93	59.109	60.546	56.549	56.23	59.43	100		
	WS11	72.8	74.549	74.549	73.547	74.11	74.6	72.986	73.1	91.8	100			WS11	59.218	57.546	53.105	56.328	56.03	55.547	54.655	56.33	84.54	100	
	OPL5	72.219	74.54	74.54	73.51	73.02	75.495	73.11	71.325	81.105	81.62	100		OPL5	60.31	58.875	49.438	58.42	58.02	55.81	54.73	58.547	67.326	65.495	100

IsoB	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5
AD45	100										
PD630	84.04	100									
LB1	83.98	98.94	100								
WS7	76.92	82.42	84.327	100							
AT1	66.767	68.82	68.82	62.83	100						
i37	57.545	60.64	61.7	58.106	65.656	100					
OPL2	65.91	64.877	64.877	59.878	66.767	83.216	100				
WS12	55.768	58.95	56.82	50	56.218	55.768	56.82	100			
WS9	50	50	50	52.327	51.72	46.659	50	42.105	100		
WS11	53.657	54.876	54.876	55.81	54.876	45.224	46.43	39.329	73.326	100	
OPL5	44.332	46.659	46.659	43.218	47.767	47.767	45.435	39.53	50	52.327	100

IsoH	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5
AD45	100										
PD630	86.328	100									
LB1	87.217	94.769	100								
WS7	88.105	91.215	91.659	100							
AT1	78.32	82.74	81.986	78.876	100						
i37	79.2	82.74	81.97	79.765	82.3	100					
OPL2	81.42	83.219	82.774	81.42	83.219	85.4	100				
WS12	73.545	70.8	73.01	70.435	68.658	70.8	69.91	100			
WS9	61.5	61.5	61.5	61.106	61.5	60.62	59.73	64.6	100		
WS11	59.11	59.656	60.44	58.22	60.81	58.767	59.438	63.656	82.22	100	
OPL5	61.106	60.218	62.439	61.5	63.327	59.73	59.73	60.62	60.218	60.81	100

IsoC	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5
AD45	100										
PD630	86.96	100									
LB1	86.96	100	100								
WS7	82.546	89.547	89.547	100							
AT1	71.768	76.11	76.11	89.436	100						
i37	78.1	84.91	84.91	84.547	78.9	100					
OPL2	81.32	87.91	87.91	89.436	73.63	87.5	100				
WS12	62.216	65.549	65.549	63.989	64.04	70.548	66.767	100			
WS9	58.7	59.04	59.04	59.52	58.33	58.33	59.52	55.326	100		
WS11	49.107	48.765	48.765	50.547	49.655	56	57.329	51.65	60.44	100	
OPL5	54.217	52.53	52.53	54.217	50	53.12	57.329	56.31	50.655	50.548	100

IsoI	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5
AD45	100										
PD630	85.71	100									
LB1	76.105	80.325	100								
WS7	85.71	91.6	76.547	100							
AT1	82.435	87.97	76.105	87.97	100						
i37	80.108	84.32	71.219	86.02	83.547	100					
OPL2	78.99	83.12	72.215	84.881	83.12	95.4	100				
WS12	65.655	67.23	66.439	65.13	63.545	61.986	62.545	100			
WS9	47.548	52.1	48.32	50.42	50.84	47.03	47.768	47.106	100		
WS11	47.9	53.436	50	52.1	51.768	49.215	49.879	48.32	79.83	100	
OPL5	43.552	47.22	45.83	46.3	47.766	46.326	46.73	45.41	50	51.61	100

IsoD	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5
AD45	100										
PD630	96.436	100									
LB1	96.436	100	100								
WS7	93.64	95.545	95.545	100							
AT1	82.41	82.41	82.41	82.41	100						
i37	71.215	72.12	72.12	71.15	72.64	100					
OPL2	73.108	72.64	71.64	70.875	70.875	83.02	100				
WS12	65.14	65.14	65.14	67.697	63.3	65.438	68.657	100			
WS9	55.21	54.217	54.217	53.985	57.878	59.109	61.436	60.22	100		
WS11	58.33	56.325	56.325	56.7	57.878	54.44	61.436	55.91	81.44	100	
OPL5	50	48.94	48.94	50	46.81	50	52.13	57.765	57.73	58.989	100

IsoJ	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5
AD45	100										
PD630	77.659	100									
LB1	78.02	97.985	100								
WS7	77.216	90.52	92.24	100							
AT1	73.55	80.6	80.6	77.659	100						
i37	71.24	73.219	74.04	74.215	70.6996	100					
OPL2	68.795	69.1	69.1	67.81	66.81	80.877	100				
WS12	66.438	67.325	67.769	68.112	64.11	65.109	64.22	100			
WS9	54.82	55.74	56.6	58.877	51.53	54.98	52.84	56.877	100		
WS11	54.82	57.989	57.989	57.02	52.54	52.84	55.9	54.659	77.699	100	
OPL5	58.82	62.01	62.01	61.657	59.54	60.7	60.326	56.109	53.04	100	

IsoE	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5
AD45	100										
PD630	84.21	100									
LB1	84.21	100	100								
WS7	83.04	87.94	87.94	100							
AT1	74.548	76.325	76.325	75.83	100						
i37	71.547	73.018	73.108	71.3	70.12	100					
OPL2	68.14	71.3	71.3	69.23	68.325	79.999	100				
WS12	61.14	62.216	62.216	61.986	60.24	59.876	58.93	100			
WS9	53.325	53.298	53.298	52.768	52.8	52.11	51.82	49.659	100		
WS11	52.877	51.62	51.62	51.879	54.13	52.215	52.3	47.32	72.655	100	
OPL5	53.436	50.878	50.878	52.768	47.21	51.13	50.64	510.96	53.325	54.548	100

AldH1	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5
AD45	-	100									
PD630	-	100									
LB1	-	99.656	100								
WS7	-	92.02	92.02	100							
AT1	-	82.22	82	80	100						
i37	-	76.439	76.439	76.61	77.51	100					
OPL2	-	75.545	75.767	75.767	72.877	82.218	100				
WS12	-	67.879	67.879	65.877	68.875	63.658	64.14	100			
WS9	-	52.12	51.989	50.656	52.656	49.546	50.765	54.13	100		
WS11	-	53.878	53.656	52.989	53.657	49.24	50.876	53.107	81.439	100	
OPL5	-	50.33	50.11	49.989	50.545	49.768	49.546	521.95	56.549	100	

IsoF	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5
AD45	100										
PD630	81.74	100									
LB1	81.74	100	100								
WS7	77.768	89.328	89.328	100							
AT1	665.96	665.96	665.96	64.74	100						
i37	60	62.32	62.32	62.03	60.436	100					
OPL2	60.658	64.106	64.106	64.545	59.876	69.3	100				
WS12	48.655	50	50	50.987	49.1	52.52	51.248	100			
WS9	43.27	43.655	43.655	43.84	43.767	47.73	47.11	41.32	100		
WS11	41.439	40.84	40.84	42.326	423.94	45.107	42.326	39.34	61.248	100	
OPL5	43.8	44.249	44.249	46.325	43.325	45.332	44.22	40	50.545	44.44	100

Supplementary Table S4. Summary of BLASTp pairwise protein identity ranges (%) for each isoprene metabolic gene categorized by taxonomic group comparison. Reported values represent the observed minimum and maximum identity percentages for each gene across G⁺:G⁺, G⁻:G⁻, and G⁺:G⁻ pairings.

Protein	Percentage homology (%)		
	G⁺:G⁺	G⁺:G⁻	G⁻:G⁻
IsoA	82.4-100	71.2-74.6	81-100
IsoE	60.2-100	47.3-54.1	53.2-100
IsoF	48.5-100	39.3-47.7	44.4-100
IsoG	68.3-100	49.4-60.7	65-100
IsoH	68.6-100	58.2-63.6	60.2-100
IsoI	61.9-100	45.4-53.4	50-100
IsoJ	64.1-100	51.5-62	52.7-100
AldH1	63.6-100	49.2-54.1	55.7-100

Supplementary Table S5. List of protein sequences from α -subunits of soluble di-iron monooxygenases (SDIMOs) used in the multiple sequence alignment, including all IsoA sequences from this study and selected non-IsoA SDIMO representatives. * are sequences included in the MmoX alignment with IsoA.

Gene	Organism	Genome accession No	GenBank Protein ID	Protein length
MmoX*	<i>Methylocella tundrae</i> T4	AJ555245.1	CAD88243.1	398
MmoX*	<i>Methylocella silvestris</i> BL2	AJ491848.1	CAD37188.1	395
MmoX*	<i>Methylocella palustris</i> BL2	AJ458535.1	CAD30366.1	397
MmoX*	<i>Methylosinus trichosporium</i> Ob3b	X55934.3	CAA39068.2	526
MmoX*	<i>Methylococcus capsulatus</i> (Bath)	M90050.3	AAB62392.3	527
MmoX*	<i>Methylomonas methanica</i> MC09	CP002738.1	AEG00068.1	527
BmoX	<i>Thauera butanivorans</i>	AY093933.3	AAM19727.1	530
ThmA	<i>Pseudonocardia tetrahydrofuranoxydans</i>	AJ296087.1	CAC10506.1	545
PrmA	<i>Rhodococcus sp. RR1</i>	HM209445.1	ADM83577.1	439
PrmA	<i>Gordonia sp. TY-5</i>	AB112920.1	BAD03956.2	545
EtnC	<i>Nocardioides sp. JS614</i>	AY772007.1	AAV52084.1	501
EtnC	<i>Mycolicobacterium chubuense</i> NBB4	GU174752.1	ACZ56346.1	514
EtnC	<i>Mycolicobacterium rhodesiae</i> JS60	AY243034.1	AAO48576.1	500
TmoA3	<i>Burkholderia cepacia</i> G4	AF349675.1	AAL50373.1	519
TmoA	<i>Pseudomonas mendocina</i> KR1	M65106.1	AAA25999.1	500
TbuA	<i>Ralstonia pickettii</i>	U04052.1	AAB09618.1	501
XamoA	<i>Xanthomonas autotrophicus</i> Py2	AJ012090.1	CAA09911.1	497
IsoA	<i>Rhodococcus sp. AD45</i>	JYOP01000009.1	KJF19164.1	507
IsoA	<i>Rhodococcus opacus</i> PD630	JH377098.1	EHI47089.1	507
IsoA	<i>Rhodococcus sp. LB1</i>	LTCZ01000014.1	KXX62729.1	507
IsoA	<i>Rhodococcus sp. WS7</i>	SCFU01000009.1	TQC36059.1	507
IsoA	<i>Mycobacterium sp. AT1</i>	MVOC01000096.1	OPX05314.1	511
IsoA	<i>Gordonia sp. i37</i>	MVPX01000257.1	OPX14991.1	506
IsoA	<i>Gordonia sp. OPL2</i>	RKME01000032.1	ROZ88020.1	496
IsoA	<i>Nocardioides sp. WS12</i>	CP053928.1	WP_182378907.1	498
IsoA	<i>Ramlibacter sp. WS9</i>	MK176346.1	AZL41290.1	497
IsoA	<i>Variovorax sp. WS11</i>	JAAGOW010000004.1	NDZ17408.1	500
IsoA	<i>Sphingopyxis sp. OPL5</i>	CP060725.1	QNO27218.1	497

Supplementary Table S6. Pairwise nucleotide identity percentages for each protein-coding in the isoprene metabolic gene cluster (IsoA–F, IsoG–J, and AldH) across 11 isoprene-degrading strains. Values were derived from BLASTn comparisons.

<i>isoA</i>	AD45	PD630	LBI	WS7	ATI	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5	<i>isoG</i>	AD45	PD630	LBI	WS7	ATI	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5	
AD45	100.0											AD45	100.0											
PD630	84.7	100.0										PD630	83.5	100.0										
LBI	84.7	99.4	100.0									LBI	77.3	76.7	100.0									
WS7	84.7	88.7	88.6	100.0								WS7	80.9	87.3	75.0	100.0								
ATI	78.7	81.8	82.1	79.7	100.0							ATI	78.1	80.6	74.7	79.5	100.0							
i37	80.4	83.8	84.0	81.7	81.7	100.0						i37	74.8	77.6	70.9	75.3	78.3	100.0						
OPL2	79.1	81.8	82.1	80.8	80.8	84.3	100.0					OPL2	74.9	77.4	71.6	74.7	77.3	79.4	100.0					
WS12	78.4	82.7	82.7	79.5	79.5	81.8	79.1	100.0				WS12	73.5	77.5	71.9	75.0	76.7	73.7	73.1	100.0				
WS9	73.0	73.4	73.5	72.7	72.7	76.3	73.4	75.4	100.0			WS9	66.1	68.1		65.9	68.1	65.2	66.7	71.0	100.0			
WS11	73.9	76.0	76.2	73.5	73.5	77.2	73.4	76.7	87.4	100.0		WS11	65.9	66.6	68.3	66.2	65.9	68.3	67.7	71.1	80.3	100.0		
OPL5	71.6	73.8	74.0	72.3	72.3	74.3	73.2	74.0	78.1	80.0	100.0	OPL5	66.9	68.5	69.8	69.2	70.4	68.2	67.9	67.6	70.7	69.8	100.0	

<i>isoA</i>	AD45	PD630	LBI	WS7	ATI	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WSH	OPL5	<i>isoG</i>	AD45	PD630	LBI	WS7	ATI	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WSH	OPL5	
AD45	100											AD45	100											
PD630	84.69	100										PD630	83.5	100										
LBI	84.69	99.41	100									LBI	77.26	76.67	100									
WS7	84.7	88.72	88.59	100								WS7	80.93	87.31	74.95	100								
ATI	78.67	81.82	82.11	79.73	100							ATI	78.08	80.6	74.71	79.52	100							
i37	80.37	83.8	83.95	81.69	81.69	100						i37	74.78	77.57	70.88	75.31	78.34	100						
OPL2	79.13	81.84	82.05	80.81	80.81	84.29	100					OPL2	74.91	77.44	71.61	74.66	77.26	79.42	100					
WS12	78.39	82.69	82.68	79.49	79.49	81.77	79.09	100				WS12	73.51	77.5	71.94	75	76.73	73.67	73.1	100				
WS9	72.97	73.35	73.49	72.68	72.68	76.32	73.35	75.4	100			WS9	66.07	68.09		65.92	68.14	65.16	66.7	70.97	100			
WSH	73.86	76.03	76.17	73.47	73.47	77.24	73.37	76.74	87.39	100		WSH	65.91	66.61	68.28	66.21	65.94	68.32	67.72	71.06	80.32	100		
OPL5	71.64	73.8	73.98	72.31	72.31	74.3	73.2	74.01	78.07	80.03	100	OPL5	66.86	68.54	69.75	69.2	70.38	68.2	67.88	67.64	70.74	69.75	100	

isoB	<u>AD45</u>	<u>PD630</u>	<u>LB1</u>	<u>WS7</u>	<u>AT1</u>	<u>i37</u>	<u>OPL2</u>	<u>WS12</u>	<u>WS9</u>	<u>WS11</u>	<u>OPL5</u>	isoH	<u>AD45</u>	<u>PD630</u>	<u>LB1</u>	<u>WS7</u>	<u>AT1</u>	<u>i37</u>	<u>OPL2</u>	<u>WS12</u>	<u>WS9</u>	<u>WS11</u>	<u>OPL5</u>
	100.0												100.0										
AD45	78.6	100.0										AD45	78.4	100.0									
PD630	77.9	98.6	100.0									PD630	78.4	93.8	100.0								
LB1	73.0	81.7	81.3	100.0								LB1	78.4	87.4	86.9	100.0							
WS7	68.9	71.5	71.2	69.7	100.0							WS7	71.8	77.6	78.3	74.5	100.0						
AT1		69.8	69.4	69.3	70.3	100.0						AT1	72.6	76.8	77.3	73.4	79.0	100.0					
i37	67.8	70.7	69.6	78.9	72.0	77.9	100.0					i37	73.7	77.3	77.1	75.2	76.5	79.2	100.0				
OPL2					65.9	77.1	65.2	100.0				OPL2	69.9	73.0	74.8	70.6	73.7	71.5	69.9	100.0			
WS12	78.6					80.8	74.5		100.0			WS12	69.9	72.0	72.6	71.2	73.3	70.7	69.4	77.1	100.0		
WS9	79.6	68.3	69.7	73.5	76.4	76.0			77.2	100.0		WS9	67.7	68.7	69.7	74.0	74.4	74.9	67.4	73.1	78.1	100.0	
WS11									81.9	76.7	100.0	WS11	61.1	60.2	62.4	61.5	63.3	59.7	59.7	60.6	60.2	60.8	100.0
OPL5												OPL5											
isoC	<u>AD45</u>	<u>PD630</u>	<u>LB1</u>	<u>WS7</u>	<u>AT1</u>	<u>i37</u>	<u>OPL2</u>	<u>WS12</u>	<u>WS9</u>	<u>WS11</u>	<u>OPL5</u>	isoI	<u>AD45</u>	<u>PD630</u>	<u>LB1</u>	<u>WS7</u>	<u>AT1</u>	<u>i37</u>	<u>OPL2</u>	<u>WS12</u>	<u>WS9</u>	<u>WS11</u>	<u>OPL5</u>
	100.0												100.0										
AD45	86.1	100.0										AD45	84.2	100.0									
PD630	86.1	100.0	100.0									PD630	77.0	80.8	100.0								
LB1	83.2	87.5	87.5	100.0								LB1	81.6	87.7	75.9	100.0							
WS7	74.0	75.9	75.9	73.3	100.0							WS7	78.5	82.9	75.5	80.1	100.0						
AT1	77.1	81.8	81.8	78.8	77.0	100.0						AT1	78.9	81.9	73.9	79.9	78.8	100.0					
i37							100.0					i37	78.0	81.1	74.9	79.2	80.3	87.1	100.0				
OPL2	70.3	75.8	75.8	73.7	75.0	74.0		100.0				OPL2	72.7	73.5	71.7	71.2	71.6	73.7	72.3	100.0			
WS12	78.5	71.2	71.2	77.4	72.8	69.9			100.0			WS12	70.2	66.4	68.6	68.7	70.7	69.4	65.2	73.8	100.0		
WS9	70.3	71.2	71.1	72.9	71.8	76.6			78.7	100.0		WS9	67.5	66.1	67.9	65.8	65.1	65.2	67.1	74.9	80.2	100.0	
WS11	73.6	74.7	74.7	72.5	72.6	70.3		71.8	73.5	72.2	100.0	WS11	72.4			66.2	65.7	64.3	67.3	67.0	67.7	68.1	100.0
OPL5												OPL5											

isoD	<u>AD45</u>	<u>PD630</u>	<u>LB1</u>	<u>WS7</u>	<u>AT1</u>	<u>i37</u>	<u>OPL2</u>	<u>WS12</u>	<u>WS9</u>	<u>WS11</u>	<u>OPL5</u>	isoJ	<u>AD45</u>	<u>PD630</u>	<u>LB1</u>	<u>WS7</u>	<u>AT1</u>	<u>i37</u>	<u>OPL2</u>	<u>WS12</u>	<u>WS9</u>	<u>WS11</u>	<u>OPL5</u>
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<u>AD45</u>	<u>100.0</u>											
<u>PD630</u>	<u>79.6</u>	<u>100.0</u>										
<u>LB1</u>	<u>79.6</u>	<u>100.0</u>	<u>100.0</u>									
<u>WS7</u>	<u>75.3</u>	<u>85.6</u>	<u>85.6</u>	<u>100.0</u>								
<u>AT1</u>	<u>67.1</u>	<u>69.1</u>	<u>69.1</u>	<u>68.4</u>	<u>100.0</u>							
<u>i37</u>	<u>65.8</u>	<u>66.9</u>	<u>66.9</u>	<u>67.2</u>	<u>66.2</u>	<u>100.0</u>						
<u>OPL2</u>	<u>68.0</u>	<u>67.3</u>	<u>67.3</u>	<u>66.0</u>	<u>68.8</u>	<u>71.3</u>	<u>100.0</u>					
<u>WS12</u>	<u>74.3</u>	<u>80.9</u>	<u>80.9</u>	<u>70.5</u>	<u>72.6</u>	<u>64.7</u>	<u>94.4</u>	<u>100.0</u>				
<u>WS9</u>	<u>95.0</u>	<u>88.9</u>	<u>88.9</u>	<u>71.3</u>	<u>72.9</u>	<u>69.5</u>			<u>100.0</u>			
<u>WS11</u>	<u>72.0</u>	<u>77.5</u>	<u>77.5</u>	<u>80.3</u>	<u>72.9</u>	<u>75.2</u>	<u>81.1</u>	<u>80.7</u>	<u>70.9</u>	<u>100.0</u>		
<u>OPL5</u>	<u>74.3</u>	<u>70.3</u>	<u>70.3</u>	<u>100.0</u>	<u>70.0</u>	<u>67.3</u>	<u>69.4</u>	<u>79.6</u>	<u>72.2</u>	<u>85.5</u>	<u>100.0</u>	

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<i>isoB</i>	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5	<i>isoH</i>	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WS11	OPL5	
	100												100											
AD45	78.6	100										AD45	78.4	100										
PD630	77.89	98.6	100									PD630	78.35	93.81	100									
LB1	72.98	81.72	81.34	100								LB1	78.41	87.37	86.87	100								
WS7	68.88	71.54	71.15	69.7	100							WS7	71.79	77.61	78.29	74.48	100							
AT1		69.78	69.4	69.29	70.3	100						AT1	72.58	76.8	77.33	73.38	78.99	100						
i37	67.8	70.72	69.58	78.85	72.02	77.93	100					i37	73.65	77.25	77.13	75.22	76.53	79.15	100					
OPL2					65.91	77.14	65.22	100				OPL2	69.94	72.98	74.78	70.59	73.73	71.54	69.9	100				
WS12						80.81	74.51	100				WS12	69.92	71.99	72.61	71.2	73.28	70.66	69.36	77.08	100			
WS9	78.57											WS9	67.67	68.7	69.7	73.95	74.37	74.85	67.4	73.06	78.09	100		
WS11	79.55	68.29	69.7	73.47	76.42	76			77.22	100		WS11	67.67	68.7	69.7	73.95	74.37	74.85	67.4	73.06	78.09	100		
OPL5									81.91	76.74	100	OPL5	61.06	60.18	62.39	61.5	63.27	59.73	59.73	60.62	60.18	60.81	100	
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<i>isoC</i>	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WSH	OPL5	<i>isoI</i>	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WSH	OPL5	
	100												100											
AD45	86.09	100										AD45	84.24	100										
PD630	86.09	100	100									PD630	77.02	80.81	100									
LB1	83.19	87.54	87.54	100								LB1	81.59	87.73	75.9	100								
WS7	74	75.94	75.94	73.33	100							WS7	78.52	82.85	75.49	80.06	100							
AT1	77.1	81.82	81.82	78.79	76.97	100						AT1	78.9	81.86	73.88	79.92	78.76	100						
i37							100					i37	78.04	81.12	74.89	79.19	80.31	87.06	100					
OPL2	70.27	75.82	75.82	73.72	75	74.01		100				OPL2	72.65	73.51	71.67	71.21	71.61	73.74	72.25	100				
WS12	78.51	71.18	71.18	77.42	72.82	69.9			100			WS12	70.2	66.4	68.64	68.72	70.67	69.37	65.2	73.76	100			
WS9	70.27	71.18	71.12	72.94	71.79	76.6			78.66	100		WS9	67.5	66.12	67.94	65.82	65.08	65.23	67.1	74.87	80.2	100		
WSH	73.61	74.74	74.74	72.49	72.64	70.33		71.77	73.45	72.22	100	WSH	72.37			66.24	65.73	64.32	67.32	67	67.73	68.05	100	
OPL5												OPL5												
<i>isoD</i>	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WSH	OPL5	<i>isoJ</i>	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WSH	OPL5	
	100												100											
AD45	89.49	100										AD45	74.79	100										
PD630	89.49	100	100									PD630	74.96	97.86	100									
LB1	87.09	92.79	92.79	100								LB1	73.5	89.46	90.31	100								
WS7	77.21	79.08	79.08	77.06	100							WS7	72.56	78.13	78.62	77.84	100							
AT1	72.79	73.36	73.36	75.62	76.6	100						AT1	70.29	72.71	72.71	73.22	69.47	100						
i37	71.29	72.7	72.7		73.99	76.95	100					i37							100					
OPL2	73.78	71.75	71.75		70.88	70	70.93	100				OPL2									100			
WS12	65.65	67.26	67.26	66.95	71.71	69.08	65.62		100			WS12	67.69	67.25	68.11	67.83	66.84	72.32			100			
WS9		69.16	69.16	67.42	71.65	69.47	68.99	69.68	80.95	100		WS9	70.59	70.45	71.18	70.97	69.12	76.99				78.07	100	
WSH						72.8	70.29			71.49	100	WSH		64.88	65.27	65.8	68.17	66.88				68.81	66.34	100
OPL5												OPL5												

	<i>isoE</i>	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WSH	OPL5	<i>aldH1</i>	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WSH	OPL5	
1		100													100										
2	AD45	79.2	100										PD630	-	99.12	100									
3	PD630	79.3	99.8	100									LB1	-	86.43	86.21	100								
4	LB1	78.29	86.61	86.8	100								WS7	-	78.1	78.17	76.32	100							
5	WS7	74.38	75.42	75.64	74.87	100							AT1	-	76.35	76.33	75.74	73.6	100						
6	AT1	71.58	72.02	72.13	72.23	73.72	100						i37	-	73.73	73.5	71.41	71.62	77.17	100					
7	i37	68.48	71.42	71.6	72.62	71.1	75.91	100					OPL2	-	71.77	71.6	70.88	69.57	70.06	68.92	100				
8	OPL2	69	70.8	71.05	68.43	68.97	71.39	67.62	100				WS12	-	67.73	67.5	65.59	67.59	68.04	65.16	69.65	100			
9	WS12	66.18	66.18	66.04	65.43	66.45	67.95	64.75	66.52	100			WS9	-	67.33	67.33	70.02	69.68	71.92	67.38	68.45	78.52	100		
10	WS9	67.11	70.96	70.59	73.94	65.55	67.76	71.97	66.18	73.65	100		WSH	-	66.27	66.57	64.06	65.16	65.04	64.66	68.13	66.72	67.23	100	
11	WSH	67.33	67.5	67.63	67.07	69.42	66.24	63.06	66.09	68	69.22	100	OPL5	-											
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21	<i>isoF</i>	AD45	PD630	LB1	WS7	AT1	i37	OPL2	WS12	WS9	WSH	OPL5													
22		100																							
23	AD45	79.56	100																						
24	PD630	79.56	100	100																					
25	LB1	75.31	85.55	85.55	100																				
26	WS7	67.11	69.05	69.05	68.41	100																			
27	AT1	65.76	66.9	66.9	67.2	66.2	100																		
28	i37	67.95	67.27	67.27	66.03	68.78	71.26	100																	
29	OPL2	74.29	80.88	80.88	70.53	72.6	64.7	94.44	100																
30	WS12	95	88.89	88.89	71.31	72.9	69.53			100															
31	WS9	71.95	77.46	77.46	80.28	72.9	75.18	81.08	80.65	70.91	100														
32	WSH	74.29	70.27	70.27	100	70	67.25	69.35	79.55	72.22	85.45	100													
33	OPL5																								
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Figure 1. Organization of the *iso* gene clusters in 11 representative isoprene-degrading bacteria. *iso* clusters containing the *isoA* gene and associated operon components were extracted from annotated genomes. Homologous genes across strains are connected by grey links, with shading indicating amino acid identity (threshold: $\geq 20\%$). Genes are coloured and labelled according to putative functions: *isoA–isoJ* encode the isoprene monooxygenase complex (including the center of the cluster *isoA–C*) and associated electron transfer proteins; *aldH1/2*, *gshA/B*, *gorA*, *marR*, and *lysR* represent adjacent genes putatively involved in regulation, redox processes, or glutathione metabolism. Strain names are shown on the left, with clusters scaled proportionally. Gene orientations reflect native operon direction. In Gram-positive strains, most *Rhodococcus* genomes harboured duplicated *isoGHIJ* modules flanking the monooxygenase genes, whereas Gram-negative strains showed a single contiguous operon. Notably, *Rh. WS1* lacked the duplicated detoxification module, retaining only a single *isoGHIJ* copy, suggesting intra-lineage structural variability.

Figure 2. SDIMO α -subunit phylogeny and placement of IsoA. Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of soluble di-iron monooxygenase (SDIMO) α -subunits showing the placement of IsoA sequences from 11 confirmed isoprene degraders (Gram-positive and Gram-negative) relative to representative SDIMO groups. One to two representative sequences were retained per major SDIMO lineage (BmoX, PrmA, ThmA, TmoA) and six MmoX sequences, together with all IsoA sequences included in this study. IsoA forms a distinct, well-supported clade separated into Gram-positive (*Rhodococcus*, *Gordonia*, *Mycobacterium*, *Nocardioides*) and Gram-negative (*Variovorax*, *Sphingopyxis*, *Ramlibacter*) subclades. The analytical procedure encompassed 29 amino acid sequences with 617 positions in the final dataset. Scale bar represents amino acid substitutions per site. Accession numbers and full taxa are provided in Supplementary Table 5.

Figure 3. Protein sequence comparison of isoprene monooxygenase α -subunit (IsoA) and soluble methane monooxygenase α -subunit (MmoX). Multiple sequence alignment of MmoX and IsoA α -subunits visualised with ESPript 3.0, using *Rh. AD45* IsoA as the structural reference for residue numbering and secondary structure annotation. Arrows indicate known or putative features of IsoA/MmoX (1) iron binding ligand residue in red, (2) implicated in methane oxidation in blue, (3) gating residue in black, (4) residues which might confer enantioselectivity in oxidation products in dark green, (5) highly conserved residue in orange, (6) hydrogen bonding (C-F helices) in grey, (7) delivery of electrons to the active site in purple, (8) tightly packed regions in brown, (9) canyon residues for protein B or oxidoreductase, (10) handle residues in light green, (11) important docking residues in teal and the letter D, and (12) residues that interacts with the gamma subunit in pink, according to Leahy *et al* (Table 2). Abbreviations of the annotated residues: H, hydrophobic residues surrounding the diiron center; S, structural residues involved in hydrogen bonding of the alpha-helices A and C; *, iron cluster ligands; D, docking residues; Fe(A), iron cluster ligands for Fe(A) iron center; Fe(B), iron cluster ligands for Fe(B) iron center. Other labels describe the location or possible function of the residue.

Figure 4. Structural comparison of IsoA and MmoX α -subunits. Two views of the cartoon representation of the α -subunit of isoprene monooxygenase (IsoA, *Rh. AD45*, cyan) predicted by AlphaFold2 and the α -subunit of soluble methane monooxygenase (MmoX, *Methylococcus capsulatus* Bath, PDB: 1MTY, blue) superimposed and visualised in PyMOL. Residues involved in iron coordination (IsoA in pink, MmoX in orange) and active site channel (IsoA in purple, MmoX in green) are highlighted in ribbon representation (IsoA in pink, MmoX in yellow) and detail annotated with residue type and position for MmoX (F4C). Location of iron atoms (red spheres in F4B, red FE in F4C) are shown in reference to sMMO in SF17 and the sMMO from 1MTY PDB model⁹. Two magnificationorientations and slight changes in orientation of the active site are shown to illustrate the conservation of the non-heme di-iron catalytic core and surrounding helices. The figure highlights both the conserved channel residues (carboxylate/histidine constellation (HXH and TN) and EXXH motifs) along with clade-specific substitutions near the active site, consistent with shared SDIMO ancestry but functional divergence for isoprene oxidation. Mean pLDDT give an overall confidence score of ~ 91.8 .

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3 **Figure 5. Predicted architecture of the IsoMO catalytic core.** Two views of the quaternary structure of the
4 isoprene monooxygenase (IsoMO) hydroxylase core from *Rh. AD45*. Multimer recovered the expected $\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$
5 oxygenase assembly, comprising an IsoA dimer (cyan), two IsoE subunits (purple), and two IsoB subunits
6 (green), closely resembling the architecture of other soluble di-iron monooxygenase (SDIMO) hydroxylases.
7 Model confidence was very high overall with most residues scoring above 90. The core fold was strongly
8 supported (pTM = 0.89), while inter-subunit interfaces showed high confidence (ipTM = 0.86), consistent with
9 a stable, well-defined catalytic assembly and limited flexibility in peripheral contact regions.
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24 **Supplementary Figure S1. Isoprene metabolic pathway in the Gram-positive model**
 25 **bacterium *Rhodococcus* sp. AD45.** HGMB, 1-hydroxy-2-glutathionyl-2-methyl-3-butene;
 26 GMB, 2-glutathionyl-2-methyl-3-butenal; GMBA, 2-glutathionyl-2-methyl-3-butenic acid;
 27 SG, glutathione; GSH, reduced glutathione; X-CoA, donor. The figure is modified from Rix
 28 *et al.*, 2023.
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Supplementary Figure S2. IsoMO core α -subunit (IsoA) sequence analysis. (A)

Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of IsoA protein sequences from 11 representative isoprene-degrading bacteria. UFBoot node-support values are shown in red. The tree was inferred from full-length protein sequences (518 amino acids). Scale bar indicates substitutions per site. (B) Multiple sequence alignment of IsoA proteins visualised with ESPrnt 3.0, based on MAFFT-trimmed alignments (507 aligned positions after removal of gaps and poorly aligned regions). (C) Two angles of the AlphaFold2 structural model of IsoA proteins from *Rh. AD45* (Gram-positive; cyan) and *V. WS11* (Gram-negative; salmon). Models were predicted with AlphaFold2 via ColabFold (default parameters). Monomeric and dimeric forms are shown, with superposition highlighting conserved α -helical/ β -sheet cores and clade-specific loop differences. Predicted iron-ligand residues are marked in red (*V. WS11*) and magenta (*Rh. AD45*, e.g. E110, H143, E237). All AlphaFold models were scored using per-residue pLDDT values; for IsoA, the mean pLDDT was ~ 91.8 , indicating high model confidence, particularly around conserved di-iron coordination residues.

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Supplementary Figure S3. IsoMO core γ -subunit (IsoB) sequence analysis. (A)

Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of IsoB protein sequences from 11 representative isoprene-degrading bacteria. UFBoot node-support values are shown in red. The tree was inferred from full-length protein sequences (95 amino acids). Scale bar indicates substitutions per site. (B) Multiple sequence alignment of IsoB proteins visualised with ESPrnt 3.0, based on MAFFT-trimmed alignments (89 aligned positions after removal of gaps and poorly aligned regions). (C) AlphaFold2 structural models of IsoB proteins from *Rh.* AD45 (Gram-positive; cyan) and *V.* WS11 (Gram-negative; salmon). Models were predicted with AlphaFold2 via ColabFold as above. Prediction confidence was high across the β 1– α 2 core (mean pLDDT > 90), with moderate scores in peripheral loops (pLDDT 70–85), indicating reliable modelling of the conserved structural framework.

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Supplementary Figure S4. The Rieske-type ferredoxin (IsoC) sequence analysis. (A) Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of IsoC protein sequences from 11 representative isoprene-degrading bacteria. UFBoot node-support values are shown in red. The tree was inferred from

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3 full-length protein sequences (126 amino acids). Scale bar indicates substitutions per site. (B)
4 Multiple sequence alignment of IsoC proteins visualised with ESPrpt 3.0, based on MAFFT-
5 trimmed alignments (89 aligned positions after removal of gaps and poorly aligned regions).
6 *Rh. AD45* was used as reference for secondary-structure annotation. Conserved cluster
7 coordination motifs CPHQ (C49–Q52) and TCRAH (T67–H71). (C) AlphaFold2 structural
8 models of IsoC proteins from *Rh. AD45* (Gram-positive; cyan) and *V. WS11* (Gram-negative;
9 salmon), were predicted with AlphaFold2 via ColabFold as above. Highlighted residues fall
10 within high-confidence regions (pLDDT > 95), supporting structural conservation across
11 Gram-positive and Gram-negative IsoC proteins.
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Supplementary Figure S5. The coupling subunit (IsoD) sequence analysis. (A) Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of IsoD protein sequences from 11 representative isoprene-degrading bacteria. UFBoot node-support values are shown in red. The tree was inferred from full-length protein sequences (113 amino acids). Scale bar indicates substitutions per site. (B) Multiple sequence alignment of IsoD proteins visualised with ESPrnt 3.0, based on MAFFT-trimmed alignments (104 aligned positions after removal of gaps and poorly aligned regions). *Rh.* AD45 was used as reference for secondary-structure annotation. (C) AlphaFold2 structural models of IsoD proteins from *Rh.* AD45 (Gram-positive; cyan) and *V.* WS11 (Gram-negative; salmon), were predicted with AlphaFold2 via ColabFold as above. Key conserved cluster coordination residues (Cys37, His39, Cys56, His59 and Glu72–Glu81) fall within high-confidence regions (pLDDT > 92), supporting their structural and functional relevance.

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3 **Supplementary Figure S6. The β -subunit of the ~~hydroxylase for the~~ IsoMO core (IsoE)**
4 **sequence analysis.** (A) Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of IsoE protein sequences from 11
5 representative isoprene-degrading bacteria. UFBoot node-support values are shown in red.
6 The tree was inferred from full-length sequences (372 amino acids). Scale bar indicates
7 substitutions per site. (B) Multiple sequence alignment of IsoE proteins visualised with
8 ESPript 3.0, based on MAFFT-trimmed alignments (339 aligned positions). *Rh.* AD45 was
9 used as reference for secondary-structure annotation. Conserved regions include a β -strand
10 region (residues 148–180) and short glycine-rich segment (residues 45-55). (C) AlphaFold2
11 models of IsoE proteins from *Rh.* AD45 and *V.* WS11 were predicted with AlphaFold2 via
12 ColabFold as above.
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Supplementary Figure S7. The reductase (IsoF) sequence analysis. A) Maximum-

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3 likelihood phylogeny of IsoF protein sequences from 11 representative isoprene-degrading
4 bacteria. UFBoot node-support values are shown in red. The tree was inferred from full-
5 length sequences (364 amino acids). Scale bar indicates substitutions per site. (B) Multiple
6 sequence alignment of IsoF proteins visualised with ESPript 3.0, based on MAFFT-trimmed
7 alignments (332 aligned positions). *Rh.* AD45 was used as reference for secondary-structure
8 annotation. Conserved motifs within IsoF include YECASG (35–40), CGxC (42–45) and
9 WAD (58–60). (C) AlphaFold2 models of IsoF from *Rh.* AD45 (cyan) and *V.* WS11 (salmon)
10 were predicted with ColabFold as above. Models showed high-confidence predictions for the
11 β -sheet/ α -helix core (mean pLDDT > 80), with lower confidence in peripheral loops and
12 variable C-terminal regions.
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3 **Supplementary Figure S8. The putative CoA-transferase (IsoG) sequence analysis.** (A)
4 Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of IsoG protein sequences from 11 representative isoprene-
5 degrading bacteria. UFBoot node-support values are shown in red. The tree was inferred from
6 full-length sequences (406 amino acids). Scale bar indicates substitutions per site. (B)
7 Multiple sequence alignment of IsoG proteins visualised with ESPript 3.0, based on MAFFT-
8 trimmed alignments (398 aligned positions). *Rh. AD45* was used as reference for secondary-
9 structure annotation. Conserved features include the candidate residues for the catalytic
10 glutamate (E) residues 33 and 392, GxG-like motifs (G36, G101 and G121). (C) AlphaFold2
11 structural models of IsoG proteins from *Rh. AD45* and *V. WS11*, were predicted with
12 AlphaFold2 via ColabFold as above, showed high model confidence (pLDDT > 95) across
13 catalytic regions.
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Supplementary Figure S9. NAD⁺-dependent dehydrogenase subunit (IsoH) sequence analysis. (A) Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of IsoH protein sequences from 11 representative isoprene-degrading bacteria. UFBoot node-support values are shown in red. The tree was inferred from full-length sequences (227 amino acids). Scale bar indicates

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3 substitutions per site. (B) Multiple sequence alignment of IsoH proteins visualised with
4 ESPrpt 3.0, based on MAFFT-trimmed alignments (226 aligned positions). *Rh.* AD45 was
5 used as reference for secondary-structure annotation. (C) AlphaFold2 structural models of
6 IsoH proteins from *Rh.* AD45 and *Variovorax* sp. WS11 were predicted with AlphaFold2 via
7 ColabFold as above.
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Supplementary Figure S10. Glutathione S-transferase-like subunit (IsoI) sequence analysis. (A) Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of IsoI protein sequences from 11 representative isoprene-degrading bacteria. UFBoot node-support values are shown in red. The tree was inferred from full-length sequences (245 amino acids). Scale bar indicates

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3 substitutions per site. (B) Multiple sequence alignment of IsoI proteins visualised with
4 ESPrpt 3.0, based on MAFFT-trimmed alignments (238 aligned positions). *Rh.* AD45 was
5 used as reference for secondary-structure annotation. A conserved GXG loop (G157–G159)
6 may contribute to glutathione binding. (C) AlphaFold2 structural models of IsoI proteins
7 from *Rh.* AD45 (cyan) and *V.* WS11 (salmon) were predicted with AlphaFold2 via ColabFold
8 as above. Predicted structures achieved high confidence (pLDDT > 90 across 92 % of
9 residues).
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Supplementary Figure S11. Glutathione S-transferase-like subunit (IsoJ) sequence analysis. (A) Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of IsoJ protein sequences from 11

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3 representative isoprene-degrading bacteria. UFBoot node-support values are shown in red.
4 The tree was inferred from full-length sequences (255 amino acids). Scale bar indicates
5 substitutions per site. (B) Multiple sequence alignment of IsoJ proteins visualised with
6 ESPript 3.0, based on MAFFT-trimmed alignments (237 aligned positions). *Rh.* AD45 was
7 used as reference for secondary-structure annotation. (C) AlphaFold2 models of IsoJ proteins
8 from *Rh.* AD45 (cyan) and *V.* WS11 (salmon) were predicted with AlphaFold2 via ColabFold
9 as above and mapped to *Rh.* AD45 numbering. Consensus sequence is included. Predicted
10 structures had mean pLDDT scores of 91.5 (*Rh.* AD45) and 89.7 (*V.* WS11).
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3 **Supplementary Figure S12. Aldehyde dehydrogenase (AldH1) sequence analysis.** (A)
4 Maximum-likelihood phylogeny of AldH1 protein sequences from 10 isoprene-degrading
5 bacteria. UFBoot node-support values are shown in red. The tree was inferred from full-
6 length sequences (480 amino acids). Scale bar indicates substitutions per site. (B) Multiple
7 sequence alignment of trimmed AldH1 sequences visualised with ESPript 3.0 (474 aligned
8 positions), mapped to *Rh. opacus* PD630 numbering. Consensus sequence is included. (C)
9 AlphaFold2 models of AldH1 proteins showed high predicted confidence, with mean pLDDT
10 scores of 95.7 (*V. WS11*) and 96.2 (*Rh. opacus* PD630).
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Supplementary Figure S13. Pairwise tree distances for protein phylogenies of the *iso* gene cluster. Heatmaps show all-versus-all distances between maximum-likelihood trees of 11 *iso* genes using four metrics: (top left) Normalised Robinson–Foulds (RF) distance, (top right) Weighted RF distance, (bottom left) Normalised subtree-prune-and-regraft (SPR) distance and (bottom right) Branch-score distance. Right-hand panels incorporate branch-length information, while left-hand panels show only topological differences. Light-blue cells indicate greater similarity between trees. Overall, low distance values indicate congruent phylogenies: oxygenase core genes (*isoA–C*) showed high congruence, detoxification genes (*isoG–J*) were more divergent and AldH1 and electron-transfer genes (*isoD–F*) displayed intermediate patterns.

Supplementary Figure S14. Distribution of pairwise tree distances, for both nucleotide and amino acid alignments Histograms show pairwise distances between *iso* gene phylogenies using four metrics: (top left) Normalised Robinson–Foulds (RF), (top right) Weighted RF, (bottom left) Normalised SPR and (bottom right) Branch-score distance. Right-hand panels incorporate branch lengths, while left-hand panels show topological differences only. Green distributions correspond to amino acid trees, and brown to nucleotide trees. Both data types yield similar distributions, though DNA trees exhibit slightly higher overall distances and spread when branch lengths are included. Oxygenase core genes (*isoA–C*) show low pairwise distances, while detoxification genes (*isoG–J*) are more divergent. AldH1 exhibits intermediate distances, reflecting partial decoupling from the core *iso* module.

Supplementary Figure S15. Multidimensional scaling (MDS) of tree distances (amino acid alignments). MDS plots display two-dimensional representations of pairwise distances between all protein-coding *iso* gene trees. Distances were calculated using four metrics: (top left) Normalised RF, (top right) Weighted RF, (bottom left) Normalised SPR and (bottom right) Branch-score distance. Right-hand panels include branch-length information, while left-hand panels reflect topological relationships only.

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3 **Supplementary Figure S16.** Multiple sequence alignment of representative soluble di-iron
4 monooxygenase (SDIMO) α -subunit (A-component) proteins. The alignment includes IsoA
5 sequences from all confirmed isoprene-degrading strains in this study, together with selected
6 representatives of other SDIMO lineages (MmoX, PrmA, BmoX, TmoA, TbuA, ThmA and
7 XamoA). Alignments were generated using MAFFT (L-INS-i) and visualised with ESPrpt
8 3.0. Residue numbering corresponds to *Methylosinus trichosporium* Ob3b (MmoX) for
9 consistency. Residues are coloured by physicochemical properties, and a consensus sequence
10 is shown beneath the alignment.
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Supplementary Figure S18. Multiple sequence alignment of IsoA and MmoX, α -subunits of the IsoMO core and sMMO, respectively. Alignment of 11 complete IsoA sequences and six MmoX sequences was generated using MAFFT (L-INS-i) and visualised with ESPrpt 3.0, with residues coloured by physicochemical properties. The structure of MmoX from *Methylococcus capsulatus* (Bath; PDB 1MTY) was used as reference for secondary-structure annotation. Residue numbering corresponds to *Methylosinus trichosporium* Ob3b (MmoX) for consistency. A consensus sequence is shown below the alignment.

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Supplementary Figure S19. Comparison of IsoA α -subunit dimers from Gram-positive and Gram-negative isoprene degraders. AlphaFold2-predicted dimeric models of the IsoA α -subunit from *Rh. AD45* (Gram-positive; cyan) and *V. WS11* (Gram-negative; salmon) were superimposed and visualised in PyMOL. Both models display conserved dimeric architecture and catalytic core, with subtle clade-specific variations in peripheral helices and loop regions that may reflect lineage-specific adaptations of IsoMO to distinct cellular environments. Mean model confidence was pLDDT = 90.8.

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3 **Supplementary Figure S20.** (A) Structural comparison between the IsoMO core and sMMO
4 hydroxylase ($\alpha_2\beta_2\gamma_2$). Superposition of the predicted *Rh.* AD45 IsoMO core (cyan) and the
5 crystal structure of the soluble methane monooxygenase (sMMO) hydroxylase from
6 *Methylococcus capsulatus* Bath (PDB: 1MTY; blue). Both complexes share the characteristic
7 $\alpha_2\beta_2$ di-iron monooxygenase architecture, with closely aligned α -helical bundles and
8 conserved di-iron centres (orange). The strong structural correspondence supports a close
9 evolutionary and mechanistic relationship between IsoMO core and other SDIMO. (B)
10 sMMO hydroxylase (1MTY), including di-iron atoms in red.
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